

National Aeronautics and Space Administration

2025 HELIOPHYSICS TECHNOLOGY ANNUAL REPORT

HEST
HELIOPHYSICS STRATEGIC TECHNOLOGY OFFICE

WELCOME

It is my pleasure to present our 2025 Heliophysics Technology Annual Report. Looking back, this year has been about much more than hitting milestones – it has been about solidifying a foundation that will drive transformative Heliophysics science for the next decade.

We find ourselves at a pivotal moment. As NASA extends its reach toward the Moon, Mars, and beyond, Heliophysics remains at the forefront of this journey, providing the critical scientific insights and technological capabilities necessary to navigate the complexities of the space environment. We are excited for this challenge and deeply grateful for the dedication of our principal investigators, their teams, and our partners.

Our mission is straightforward but vital: we aim to incentivize, catalyze, develop, and infuse innovative technologies into space-flight missions rapidly and reliably. With the 2024 Decadal Survey now in hand, we have a clear, community-driven roadmap that anchors our investment priorities and directs our focus toward the most critical technology gaps.

What stands out most this year is the power of our community. Through efforts like our joint symposia and the expansion of our Pathfinder initiatives, we are successfully bridging the gap between laboratory innovation and the space environment. We are seeing a steady increase in these technologies making their way into operational missions, which is a direct result of your hard work and vision.

Thank you for making 2025 such a purposeful year. We are excited to share these highlights with you and look forward to the challenges that lie ahead.

Roshanak
 Roshanak Hakimzadeh, PhD
 HESTO Lead

2025 YEAR IN REVIEW

Building the Foundation for the Future

Innovation is rarely a singular event – it is a cumulative process. In 2025, the Heliophysics Technology program focused on solidifying the essential groundwork necessary to drive discoveries over the next decade. Our efforts centered on emerging technologies designed to advance the state-of-the-art in instrumentation, ultimately pushing the boundaries of what is possible in Heliophysics science. By fostering new collaborations and refining our selection processes, we have built a robust foundation for the future.

Strategic Solicitations and Space Weather: In alignment with NASA's Science Mission Directorate (SMD) and a commitment to excellence, we solicited the 2025 ROSES Heliophysics Technology and Instrument Development (H-TIDeS) using the Dual-Anonymous Peer Review (DAPR) format. This transition ensures the focus of evaluations remains squarely on merit, technical feasibility, and the potential for enabling future science and exploration.

Furthermore, we have strategically developed our ROSES H-TIDeS announcement to align not only with the 2024 Decadal Survey but with broader NASA initiatives while specifically addressing critical space weather needs. This alignment ensures our portfolio remains responsive to the most pressing challenges in safeguarding humanity's home in space and understanding the Sun-Earth connection.

Suborbital Success and Pathfinder Growth: A major highlight of the past year was the resounding success of our joint HELIOTECH and Suborbital Program Symposium. This effort served as a bridge, fostering invaluable networking between technologists, suborbital Principal Investigators (PIs), and the Flight Opportunities Program.

We also continued to expand our solicitation for Pathfinder projects, successfully selecting three new initiatives this year. These projects are vital to maturing promising technology investments through flight opportunities, reducing risk for future missions by ensuring high-impact technologies are mission-ready, and increasing the total number of technology infusions across the Heliophysics portfolio.

Notably, our most recent Pathfinder call successfully identified available suborbital rides, and we were very pleased to see proposals effectively utilizing these opportunities to bridge the gap between the laboratory and the space environment.

Building on this momentum, we are excited to announce the 2026 joint HELIOTECH and Orbital Flight Symposium, which will be held at the Johns Hopkins Applied Physics Laboratory (APL) the week of August 31, 2026. Our objective is to catalyze collaborations between the technology and Research and Technology Flight communities, specifically focusing on accelerating the infusion of mature technologies into HFORT missions.

As we close out 2025, we celebrate the progress made in bridging the gap between laboratory discovery and exploration of the space environment. We invite our community of scientists, engineers, and visionaries to join us in embracing the challenges that lie ahead.

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PORTFOLIO OVERVIEW

The technology portfolio is ROSES elements B.6 **Heliophysics Technology and Instrument Development for Science (H-TIDeS)** and B.10 **Heliophysics Flight Opportunity Studies (H-FOS)**.

HELIOSPHERE

ITM

MAGNETOSPHERE

SOLAR SCIENCE

INTERDISCIPLINARY

In support of HTP's mission of investment, advancement, maturation, and infusion of Heliophysics-funded technologies, HESTO will:

Invest in the Right Technologies

Conduct regular assessments of technology gaps to guide strategic investments and incentivize bold technologies.

Increase Likelihood of Success

Nurture technology project maturation throughout the project lifecycle.

Promote Infusion

Identify and facilitate flight opportunities for application of new technologies and mission concepts to enable and expand science for the benefit of all.

Facilitate Collaboration

Provide community events, forums, and tools that bring scientists and technologists together to develop new and transformative technologies, mission concepts, and applications.

2025 ROSES Opportunity • Proposals Due: April 15, 2026

We are excited to announce **2025 ROSES/B.6 H-TIDeS** was released as a ROSES 2025 amendment on January 12, 2026. In 2026, H-TIDeS is solicited in the Dual Anonymous Peer Review (DAPR) format. This NASA Research Announcement solicits technologies that are forward leaning, enable science in the next decade and beyond, help safeguard humanity's home in space, and support NASA's return to the Moon and exploration of Mars.

ROSES/HFOS was not solicited in 2025.

- Line Survey and Density Sensitivity Studies in Support of Hinode, MUSE, and Solar-C PI: Daniel Savin, Columbia University 24-HTIDS24-0002
- Laboratory Study of Asymmetric Reconnection Including Diamagnetic Suppression PI: Jan Egedal, University of Wisconsin, Madison 24-HTIDS24-0003
- Next-Generation Solar Neutron Tracking (SONTRAC) Instrument PI: Georgia de Nolfo, NASA's GSFC 24-HTIDS24-0005
- Shuttered Plasma Instrument for Detecting Environmental Response (SPIDER) PI: Shawn Liang, APL 24-HTIDS24-0006
- High-Rate X-ray Spectrometer for Solar and Space Physics PI: Lindsay Glesener, University of Minnesota 24-HTIDS24-0022
- Development of next generation compact time-of-flight plasma instruments for Heliophysics exploration PI: Gregory Miller, Southwest Research Institute 24-HTIDS24-0025
- A Magnetometer Based on Magneto-Optical Effects for Space Applications PI: Maria Usanova, University of Colorado, Boulder 24-HTIDS24-0036
- A High Geometric Factor, 3D-Cylindrical And Tiny Spectrometer (3D-CATS) for fast plasma measurements on future missions PI: Dharendra Kataria, Southwest Research Institute 24-HTIDS24-0039
- The Scotopic Solar Activity X-ray Imager SmallSat (SSAXI-SmallSat) PI: Chris Moore, Smithsonian Astrophysical Observatory 24-HFOS24-0008
- Ultraviolet Imaging of Earth's Auroral Oval from a Cubesat PI: Greg Holsclaw, University of Colorado, Boulder 24-HFOS24-0013

2023

- Laboratory XUV Spectroscopy: Increasing the Scientific Return of Solar Missions PI: Amy Gall, SAO 23-HTIDS23-0008
- Study of electron acceleration during magnetic reconnection by soft x-ray tomography PI: Jongsoo Yoo, Princeton University 23-HTIDS23-00011
- Hybrid AC/DC Magnetometer with Attitude Determination and Control System PI: Mark Moldwin, University of Michigan 23-HTIDS23-0001
- Optics for Compact Two-dimensional Energetic Atom (OCTEA) PI: Jerry Goldstein, Southwest Research Institute 23-HTIDS23-0004
- Development of the Suprathermal Particle and Relativistic Electron Magnetic Spectrometer (SuPREMeS) PI: Drew Turner, APL 23-HTIDS23-00012
- Scanning Coronal and Heliospheric Imager (SCHI) PI: Juliana Vievering, APL 23-HTIDS23-0016
- A Miniature Solar Wind Sensor (MSWIS) for future low-cost, constellation, and deep-space missions PI: Keiichi Ogasawara, Southwest Research Institute 23-HTIDS23-0017
- A Spaceborne Vacuum Ultraviolet (VUV) Fourier Transform Spectrometer (FTS) PI: Ed Thiemann, University of Colorado, Boulder (LASP) 23-HTIDS23-0022
- Development and Testing of a Multi-Needle Langmuir Probe for the Detection of Extremely Small Spatial Structures in Low Earth Orbit PI: Aroh Barjatya, Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University 23-HTIDS23-0023
- A New HOPE for Ionospheric Outflow and Cold Magnetospheric Plasma Measurements PI: Carlos Maldonado, LLNL 23-HTIDS23-0024
- Multi-detector Experiment for next-Generation Applications in Heliophysics (MEGA-H) PI: Joshua Eskin, Ball Aerospace 23-HTIDS23-0025
- CubeSat: On the Radiation belt electron Acceleration (CORA) PI: Hong Zhao, Auburn University 23-HFOS23-0003

2022

- Production Pathways of the OH Meinel Band Emission Required for TIMED/SABER Observations PI: Konstantinos Kalogerakis, SRI International 22-HTIDS22-0008
- Scaling Studies of Seeded Alfvén Wave Parametric Decay Instability in the Laboratory PI: Feiyu Li, New Mexico Consortium 22-HTIDS22-0019
- Goddard Miniature Coronagraph PI: Jeffrey Newmark, NASA's GSFC 22-HTIDS22-0004
- Solar Neutron TRACKing Instrument (SONTRAC) Follow-on PI: Georgia de Nolfo, NASA's GSFC 22-HTIDS22-0005
- Lightsheet Anomaly Resolution And Debris Observation-Neuromorphic (LARADO-N) PI: Andrew Nicholas, NRL 22-HTIDS22-0006 interdisciplinary
- HIRSL: a High-Resolution Spectrograph in Lyman alpha PI: Majd Mayyasi, Boston University 22-HTIDS22-0007
- Measuring Plasma Parameters and Waves in the Ionosphere of Earth PI: Mihailo Martinovic, University of Arizona, Tucson 22-HTIDS22-0013
- Debris and meteoroid ENvironment Sensor (DENTS): Instrument Technology Development PI: David Malaspina, University of Colorado, Boulder 22-HTIDS22-0014 interdisciplinary
- Development and Testing of a Miniaturized Double Langmuir Probe for Small-satellite Platforms PI: Robert Clayton, Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University 22-HTIDS22-0018
- Space Debris Detection and Characterization Using an in situ LIDAR Sensor Platform PI: John McVey, Aerospace Corp 22-HTIDS22-0020
- Miniaturized Charging Mitigation Shell Instrument for Magnetospheric Cold Plasma Sensors PI: Justin Lee, Aerospace Corp 22-HTIDS22-0023
- Satellite Space Weather Investigation Frontier (SWIFT) PI: Mojtaba Akhavan-Tafti, University of Michigan, Ann Arbor 22-HFOS22-0001
- Space Weather Impact on Planetary Emissions (SWIPE) PI: Mary Knapp, MIT 22-HFOS22-0002 interdisciplinary
- Satellite Auroral Plasma Sounders (SAPS) PI: Alex Chartier, Johns Hopkins University 22-HFOS22-0003
- Loss Through Auroral Microburst Pulsations Satellite (LAMPsat) Flight Opportunity Study PI: Mykhaylo Shumko, APL 22-HFOS22-0007

PORTFOLIO OVERVIEW

2021

- Exploring 3D Collisionless Magnetic Reconnection in the Laboratory PI: Jan Egedal, University of Wisconsin, Madison 21-HTIDS21-0003
- Development of Grotifer: a CubeSat for Three-dimensional Electric Field Measurements PI: Solène Lejosne, University of California, Berkeley 21-HTIDS21-0002
- High-Frequency Magnetic Loop for Heliophysics Exploration PI: Xiaojia Zhang, University of California, Los Angeles 21-HTIDS21-0004
- An Imaging Polarimeter for Hydrogen Lyman- α PI: Sam Tun Beltran, NRL 21-HTIDS21-0010
- Low-resource Instrumentation for Scientific Measurements in Planetary Thermospheres PI: James Clemmons, University of New Hampshire 21-HTIDS21-0012
- Dual Cluster Mission Concept Study PI: Xinlin Li, University of Colorado, Boulder 21-HFOS21-0001
- LabOratory for the Behavior of the SloT Region (LOBSTR) PI: Rachael Filwett, Univ of Iowa 21-HFOS21-0002

2020

- Study of Coronal X-ray Jet Formation Using Advanced Numerical Simulations and Laboratory Experiments PI: Masaaki Yamada, Princeton University 20-HTIDS20-0017
- Lower Hybrid Drift Waves and Associated Electron Heating During Guide Field Reconnection PI: Hantao Ji, Princeton University 20-HTIDS-0-0018
- Solar Imaging Metasurface Polarimeter (SIMPo) PI: Roberto Casini, UCAR 20-HTIDS20-0002
- Advancement of a Lyot Filter Demonstration Instrument (LFDI) for Space-borne Solar Physics Investigations PI: Scott Sewell, UCAR 20-HTIDS20-0004
- Plasma Radiation Combined IN-situ Instrument (PRCINI) PI: Ian Cohen, APL 20-HTIDS20-0009 interdisciplinary
- LIEFSI – Laboratory Investigation of Electric Field Sensor Instabilities PI: John Bonnell, University of California, Berkeley 20-HTIDS20-0010
- Development of an EMCCD Space Camera for UV Spectroscopy: Probing Nitric Oxide in the Polar Night PI: Leon Harding, VA Polytec 20-HTIDS20-0015
- Development of a Novel Nano-Transmitter Plasma Wave Antenna PI: Bill Amatucci, NRL 20-HTIDS20-0020
- Multi Look-Direction Magnetic Electron Spectrometer for Auroral Studies PI: Robert Michell, NASA's GSFC 20-HTIDS20-0021
- Mass Spectrometry of the Turbopause Region (MSTR) PI: Chad Fish, Orion Space Solutions 20-HTIDS20-0027
- CLASS, a Compact Lyman-Alpha Spatial Heterodyne Spectrometer PI: Seyedeh Sona Hosseini, NASA's JPL 20-HTIDS20-0028
- Increasing the Dynamic Range of Spaceflight Charged Particle Instruments PI: Christopher Mouikis, University of New Hampshire, Durham 20-HTIDS20-0031
- Miniaturized High-Energy-Resolution relativistic electronic Telescope (HERT)-Auburn PI: Hong Zhao, Auburn University 20-HTIDS20-0034
- MAGnetometers for Innovation and Capability (MAGIC) PI: David Miles, University of Iowa 22-PROJ-0001
- Plasmasphere Tomography (PlaTo) Mission Study PI: Wendy Frank, University of Colorado, Boulder 20-HFOS20-0011

H-TIDeS

The technology portfolio is ROSES elements B.6 **Heliophysics Technology and Instrument Development for Science** (H-TIDeS) and B.10 **Heliophysics Flight Opportunity Studies** (H-FOS).

H-FOS

H-FOS supports Heliophysics science mission concept studies at the pre-Phase A level.

H-TIDeS includes the **Laboratory Nuclear, Atomic, and Plasma Physics** (LNAPP) and **Instrument Technology Development** (ITD) focus areas. **LNAPP** supports studies that probe fundamental nuclear, atomic, and plasma physical processes and produce chemical and spectroscopic measurements that support spacecraft observations and atmospheric models. **ITD** includes innovative instrument and technology development that may be proposed as candidate experiments for future space flight opportunities.

ITD

LNAPP

2019
2018

- Fe IX Line Survey and Density Sensitivity Studies in Support of the NASA Heliophysics Program PI: Daniel Savin, Columbia University 19-HTIDS19-0005
- Medium Energy Electron Telescope (MEET) PI: Xinlin Li, University of Colorado 19-HTIDS19-0001
- Technology Development of High Speed CMOS Detectors and Multilayer Mirrors for Dynamic Solar Soft X-Ray Spectral Imaging PI: Christopher Moore, Smithsonian Astrophysical Observatory 19-HTIDS19-0017
- ACSEPT: A Compact Solar Energetic Particle Telescope PI: Brian Walsh, Boston University 19-HTIDS19-0019
- Development and Demonstration of an All Solid-State 4.7 THz Spectrometer Enabling Measurements of Thermospheric Winds, Temperature, and O Density PI: Sam Yee, Princeton University 19-HTIDS19-0027
- CHIMERA: A Hybrid Search Coil and Fluxgate Magnetometer for Small Spacecraft Missions PI: David Miles, University of Iowa 18-HTIDS18-0010
- Small UV Imager for Heliophysics Science Investigations PI: Thomas Immel, Space Sciences Laboratory/University of California, Berkeley 18-HTIDS18-0060

HELIOSPHERE

Investigations into the origins and behavior of the solar wind, energetic particles, and magnetic fields in the heliosphere, including their interactions with Earth, other planets, and the interstellar medium

ITM

Investigations into the physics of Earth's ionosphere, thermosphere, and mesosphere, including their coupling to the Earth's lower atmosphere and to the magnetosphere

MAGNETOSPHERE

Investigations into the physics of the magnetosphere, including the fundamental interactions of plasmas and particles with fields and waves and their coupling to the solar wind and ionosphere

SOLAR SCIENCE

Investigations into the Sun, including the processes taking place throughout the solar interior and atmosphere, as well as the evolution and cyclic activity of the Sun

INTERDISCIPLINARY

Investigations that relate to at least two science regimes

COLLABORATION WITH NASA STMD

NASA's Space Technology Mission Directorate (STMD) Small Business Innovation Research/Small Business Technology Transfer (SBIR/STTR) program is part of America's Seed Fund, the nation's largest source of early-stage funding for innovative technologies. This program provides funding and non-monetary support to entrepreneurs, startups, and small businesses to build, mature, and commercialize technologies that advance NASA missions and help to solve important problems facing America. Featured are some Heliophysics-relevant projects.

PHASE I | Idea Generation

Improved Probabilistic Forecasts of Solar Energetic Particles with MagPy

Predictive Science Incorporated | California
\$14.01-1001

This project will enhance MagPy with cutting-edge forecasting accuracy by integrating precise solar data, magnetic connectivity, refined algorithms, and advanced statistical/ML validation techniques. This will improve forecast accuracy and account for uncertainties, critical information for high-stakes missions like NASA Artemis. It will help improve astronaut and equipment safety against solar hazards, optimize mission planning, and extend satellite lifespans, enhancing space exploration and monitoring. Using open-source resources ensures it will be accessible to the broader community.

Global Forecasting of Earth's Electron Radiation Belts with Data Assimilation

Space Sciences Innovations, Inc | Washington
\$14.01-1011

No US capability currently provides global forecasts of the energetic particle conditions spacecraft encounter in Earth's magnetosphere. This work bridges the gap between advancing physical understanding and improving operational products. The team's physics-based prediction model has been refined over 15+ years of research incorporating magnetospheric physics processes. The project transitions this state-of-the-art physical model into an operational model. Resulting forecasts can be tailored to specific user needs and incorporated into NASA's CCMC for distribution.

Producing a Benchmark HASDM Forecast Density Database

Space Environment Technologies | California
\$14.01-1022

This work facilitates improved forecasting through a High Accuracy Satellite Drag Model (HASDM) forecast density database spanning a solar cycle (2013-2027). HASDM can become a forecasting benchmark of current US operational capabilities and facilitate community-wide density forecasting research and development. HASDM is the first step toward improved density forecasting to benefit low Earth orbit operations. This work will also extend the existing Space Environment Technologies (SET) HASDM nowcast density database (2000-2019) into 2025.

Space Weather Alerting Platform (SWAP)

Acme AtronOmatic, LLC (dba MyRadar) | Florida
\$14.01-1038

Space weather forecasting lacks the spatial and temporal resolution needed for effective nowcasting. The team proposes an innovative approach to enhanced space weather prediction using MyRadar's SWAP. SWAP leverages onboard AI to improve real-time space weather monitoring. Proliferated space weather observations deployed to cislunar and interplanetary space would provide automated, low-latency analysis of solar particle and photon spectra. These observations would benefit research and nowcasting space weather applications, improving safety and resilience of critical infrastructure.

High Performance Modeling of Space Weather Effects for Lunar Missions Operations Support

Tech-X Corp | Colorado
\$14.01-1041

New innovations to RSim will provide advanced space weather sources and unlimited scale of speed using remote resources. Current and future NASA missions will benefit, as it will allow NASA to streamline monitoring equipment design and shielding to ensure human safety and protect instrument electronics in space. A group at NASA JSC is interested using it to improve radiation transport simulations and compare results to existing codes, as well as for improving neutron radiation monitor design.

Meta-optic Spectropolarimeter for Heliophysics Imaging

Nanohmics, Inc | Texas
\$14.02-1009

Providing imaging, polarimetry, and spectroscopy in a single compact, low-cost package, this sensor is ideal for heliophysics measurements—initially in red wavelengths to investigate H-alpha, but extensible to other visible spectral bands. It will enable detailed investigation of the chromosphere, including reconnection spots along the solar limb. It also will be valuable to the petroleum, electric power, and microelectronics sectors, plus has uses for defense, water resource monitoring, intelligence, surveillance, and other military applications.

Low-Energy Charged-Particle Detection via an Avalanche Silicon Detector coupled to an Amorphous Silicon Active Layer

Amphionic LLC | Michigan
\$14.02-1015

This technology will help mitigate the effects space radiation on astronauts and assets. It provides a low-bias, -power, and -cost, rugged, compact package for solar weather monitoring, planetary exosphere studies, and heliospheric characterization. By correlating solar particle emissions with the driving feature near the photosphere, it can help identify origins and causes of the solar wind, solar energetic particles, and the Sun's magnetic field. Initial infusion could be as a solar weather monitor for NASA Artemis.

Sodium Excitation Laser for Mesospheric Analysis (SELMA)

Opto-Atomics Corp | California
\$14.02-1008

SELMA will advance NASA global wind and temperature profiling goals and aligns with future missions. Sodium layer lidar observations provide information about temperature, mesopause winds, and wave activity in the upper atmosphere. These measurements reveal how lower atmosphere energy and momentum impact near-space environments and can refine global circulation models. SELMA enables precise measurements of atmospheric temperature, winds, and gravity waves, crucial to understanding space weather and refining predictions of space and atmospheric weather interactions.

https://www.nasa.gov/sbir_sttr/

PHASE II | Prototype Development

An Advanced Surface Flux Transport Model for Space Weather

Predictive Science Inc | San Diego, CA
www.preds-ci.com
\$14.01-1005

The solar magnetic field (B) plays a key role in solar and heliophysics and is a crucial input to space weather models. This input is in the form of full-Sun maps of B. Standard observatory maps are constructed diachronically and contain data that is as much as 27 days old. Assimilative Surface Flux transport (SFT) models can improve upon this input by incorporating known surface flows and processes to produce a continuous approximation of the state of the photospheric magnetic field as a sequence maps. These synchronous maps can allow space weather models to produce more accurate results. To assess the uncertainty and sensitivity of the solutions, SFTs should produce multiple map realization sequences. Available SFTs, none of which are open source, are based on legacy code that can computationally provide only a small number of low-resolution realizations within a practical amount of time. In Phase I, the team developed Open-source Flux Transport for Space Weather Applications (OFTSWA), an advanced SFT that acquires and assimilates magnetograms and produces multiple high-resolution realizations that estimate the present state of the Sun's surface magnetic field. In Phase II, the team will deliver an updated OFTSWA and a living database of map realizations with interfaces and tools that allow rapid assessment of the maps' fidelity for space weather models and applications. OFTSWA will be beneficial to NASA's Community Coordinate Modeling Center (CCMC), especially for supporting the Moon to Mars Space Weather Analysis Office. Beyond NASA, NOAA's Space Weather Prediction Center and the Air Force also require solar magnetic map inputs to space weather models.

THz Mixers, Receivers, and O Sources for Heliophysics

Virginia Diodes, Inc | Charlottesville, VA
vadiodes.com
\$14.02-1010

Virginia Diodes, Inc's primary goal is to develop receivers and sources that can be extended throughout the 1 to 5 terahertz (THz) range for commercial and scientific applications. The pathway to achieving this goal is initially focusing on the most promising receiver technologies to enable NASA missions to measure the neutral oxygen (OI) lines at 2.06 THz and 4.75 THz for Heliophysics. This project has five objectives: 1) Development of a fundamental mixer to be used with a Quantum Cascade Lasers (QCL) Local Oscillator (LO) source for Heliophysics at 4.75 THz. This project supports mixer development (not QCL development). 2) Development of a 4.75 THz microwatt test source for the evaluation of the Virginia Diodes, Inc mixer and NASA receiver system (mixer and QCL LO). 3) Development of a 1.03 THz LO source for 2.06 THz Heliophysics receivers with a goal of >2.0 mW and minimal size, weight, and power (SWaP) for smallsat applications. 4) Development of a 2.06 THz subharmonically pumped mixer. and 5) Integration of the LO source and mixer to realize a deliverable 2.06 receiver system meeting the core requirements for a Heliophysics mission. The NASA funding will be used for design, diode-IC fabrication, assembly, testing, and evaluation, power amplifier Monolithic Microwave Integrated Circuit (MMICs), and custom machined waveguide housings. The initial target market is atmospheric remote sensing and Heliophysics research. Additional markets include plasma diagnostics for nuclear fusion experiments, QCL phase locking and testing, and general testing and measurements. The components developed for the sources can also be marketed for commercial and scientific applications.

Commercial Data Assimilation Tool for Operational Thermospheric Density

Space Environment Technologies | Pacific Palisades, CA
spacewx.com
\$14.01-1017

With the rising popularity and establishment of smallsat constellations, Low Earth Orbit (LEO) is becoming more congested. Accordingly, US agencies, companies, and international organizations have growing interest in managing LEO collision hazards. Improved thermospheric density nowcasts and forecasts are a critical need identified by the Space Weather Operations, Research, and Mitigation (SWORM) Working Group, a US federal government interagency coordinating body. To fulfill this need, this work will provide a commercial data assimilation (DA) tool that combines a variety of data sources to provide a corrected global density state. That nowcast corrected global density state can then be combined with Space Environment Technologies (SET) operational forecast space weather indices to produce a forecast global density state 2 to 3 days into the future. With a team of investigators that has deep experience with the development of High Accuracy Satellite Drag Model (HASDM), this work will fully construct Solari, a commercial DA tool that assimilates radar tracking data and Space Force Energy Dissipation Rates (EDRs) from calibration satellites to correct multiple background density models simultaneously and produce a global density state. The end goal is an operational commercial density nowcast and forecast data stream, with corresponding their uncertainties, that offers accuracy comparable to that of HASDM. This commercial DA tool will have a flexible architecture that allows for future expansion with additional measurement data sources, such as satellite Global Positioning System (GPS) data. SET considered four growth cases for this commercial DA tool that will improve thermosphere density forecasts: civilian agency satellites, defense applications, commercial satellites, and space traffic management.

Six-Meter Antenna and Boom System for CubeSats

Heliospace Corp | Berkeley, CA
helio.space
\$14.02-1013

Heliospace Corp proposes accelerated development of a modular, cubeat-scale, 6.5 mm free coil (FC) diameter, 6-m length, passively deployed antenna and instrument boom system. Although Heliospace has produced similar antennas up to 2.7-m deployed length, demonstrating feasibility beyond 3-m requires a focused research and development effort. Heliospace Corp and its partners have continued to develop a new type of Beryllium copper (BeCu) helical element, with production methods that it successfully scaled down, achieving Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 4 in Phase I. The elements are ready for application in a new cubesat-class family of Heliospace Spiral Actuated Boom, Extended and Rigidized (SABER) products. In Phase II, Heliospace will develop and qualify multiple configurations to TRL 6. New, highly compact SABER root stabilizing mechanisms are the minimum required advancement for the next generation of antennas and cubesat-scale applications. New specialized tethers and payout systems, including compact brakes and slip rings, are required for instrumented boom applications. Proving the capability of producing highly flexible tethers with embedded conductors and the means of supporting the deployment of tensile loads for deployed sensors is critical for such instrumented booms. The technical innovations made through this project will result in a significant increase in achievable deployed length over previous cubesat-scale antenna and boom systems, as well as improved accuracy, precision and repeatability of form and rigidity, and reduced disturbance of small-craft dynamics during deployment. The innovations will also reduce the engineering time needed to adapt systems to specific applications and eliminate the manufacturing time associated with the iterative deployment testing and tuning currently necessary for bespoke solutions.

66
Active Projects

3
Patents

40
Peer Reviewed
Publications

3
Pathfinders
Awarded

2
Special
Projects

10
Mission Studies
(H-FOS)

54
Technology
Development
(H-TIDeS)

3
NASA Centers

29
PI Institutions

13
Non-Heliophysics
Technologists

48
Co-I Institutions

175
Co-Is

10
Laboratory
Studies
(LNAPP)

4
Federal Agencies,
FFRDCs, & UARCs

20
PI States

17
Co-I States

6
Co-I/Collab Countries

44
Instrument
Tech Development
(ITD)

33
Universities

60
PIs

108
Students

37
First-Time PIs

HEST

BY THE NUMBERS

2025 STATS

*Only includes projects active in 2025, not those awarded in January 2026.

SMD TECHNOLOGY HIGHLIGHTS

Making High Fidelity Fluxgate Cores for Space Science & Space Weather Missions

A NASA-sponsored team at the University of Iowa (UI) is restoring and advancing the nation's capability to make high-fidelity magnetic field measurements needed to investigate space weather that can impact our communication and power grids on Earth and our assets in space.

Fluxgate magnetometers are widely-used space science and space weather instruments, but they depend on a legacy component—a ferromagnetic core—that was developed and manufactured for the U.S. Navy using technology that has been subsequently lost to the civilian community.

The UI team manufactures new fluxgate cores using a method that does not rely on legacy processes or materials and then integrates these cores into modern spaceflight magnetometers. The ferromagnetic cores are produced starting from base metal powders that are melted into custom alloys, rolled into thin foils, formed into the desired geometry of the fluxgate core, and artificially aged using heat to optimize their magnetic properties. The resulting cores are integrated into a complete fluxgate sensor ready for spaceflight applications.

Integration of the SWIM sensor for the ICI-5bis Sub-orbital Sounding Rocket.

Designing, prototyping, and manufacturing the cores, sensors, and paired electronics in house allows the team to explore new sensor geometries that are compatible with different missions. Most recently, the UI team developed a new core to be used in the Space Weather Iowa Magnetometer (SWIM). While the SWIM core is based on a core previously developed for the MAGIC Tesseract sensor that recently launched on NASA's TRACERS (Tandem Reconnection and Cusp Electrodynamics

Reconnaissance Satellites) mission the SWIM core is miniaturized and retains the same level of performance. The first flight opportunity for the SWIM fluxgate is on the University of Oslo's ICI-5bis sounding rocket mission that is scheduled to launch in winter 2025/2026 from the Andoya Space Sub-Orbital range in Norway.

Fluxgate magnetometers sense the magnetic field by detecting the electromagnetic force (EMF) induced by the changing magnetic flux. Current is driven into the drive winding (the interior winding on the fluxgate core) creating a magnetic field. When the ferromagnetic material in the cores experiences the magnetic field, its relative permeability (the intrinsic magnetic property of the metal within the core) changes. As the relative permeability changes, a voltage is induced in the sense winding (the outer winding on the core). By knowing the amount of current driven into the core and the voltage that was induced in the sense winding, we can understand the magnetic field that the sensor is experiencing. Most in-space magnetometers are not located onboard the main body of the spacecraft; instead, they are placed on booms to ensure that the magnetic fields produced by the electronics and magnetic materials onboard the spacecraft do not interfere with the sensor.

Example noise plot of a SWIM fluxgate core showing <math>< 5 \text{ pT}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}</math> at 1 Hz noise performance.

The manufacturing process for these new cores is now well documented and ~90% of the cores produced have a noise floor that is comparable or better than previous legacy cores. Consequently, UI can reliably mass-produce cores for the SWIM payload and potential future follow-on missions.

The Tesseract sensor from the MAGIC payload on the TRACERS mission (Left). The SWIM sensor (Right) is more compact, simpler to assemble, and provides equal or better performance in the relevant figures of merit (mass, power, volume, magnetic noise, offset, etc.) Image Credit: NASA's GSFC

The new SWIM magnetometer design reflects three significant changes compared to the previous MAGIC instrument. The sensor has been simplified and shrunk. Its power consumption has been reduced without sacrificing measurement performance. Both these changes aid its accommodation on a magnetometer boom. In addition, the topology of the paired electronics in each magnetometer channel has been redesigned, which allows use of lower-performance parts that tolerate a higher radiation exposure.

Reduced Sensor size: The compact SWIM design reduces the sensor size by ~30% compared to the MAGIC sensor, with further reduction to the sensor mass likely as the mechanical design is optimized. The MAGIC Tesseract design used six cores whereas the SWIM sensor utilizes three smaller cores of the same geometry. Mass is a major performance driver for deployable boom design and vehicle dynamics. The SWIM sensor can also be manufactured with a lightweight carbon-composite cover (or the cover can be omitted) to achieve a sensor mass of ~110 g, which would enable the sensor to be easily accommodated on small satellite booms.

Reduced Power consumption: Using three smaller cores with improved metallurgy instead of six large racetrack cores reduced the power consumption of the SWIM sensor by a factor of two compared to the MAGIC sensor. Although this power reduction is modest compared to the total consumption of the instrument, it positively impacts the capability for boom deployment. Significant reduction in heat dissipation at the sensor minimizes the spot-heating of the deployable boom and reduces thermal gradients that can drive boom deformation/rotation, which impacts the pointing knowledge at the sensor. These improvements to the sensor have been achieved without impacting the measurement fidelity. In fact, prototype miniaturized SWIM race-track cores are outperforming the previous MAGIC cores due to their improved metallurgy.

Updated Electronics Topology: The MAGIC electronics use a traditional analog demodulator fluxgate and magnetic feedback design. This design requires high-performance components to be able to resolve small variations in large ambient magnetic fields. There are radiation limitations to these high-performance components making it difficult for the MAGIC design to operate in a high-radiation environment. To mitigate these issues, the SWIM design employs digital demodulation instead of analog demodulation and provides magnetic feedback via temperature-compensated, digital, pulse-width-modulation. This update to the electronics enables SWIM to potentially be used in long-duration and/or high-reliability operational applications such as radiation belt missions or planetary missions with long cruise phases.

The SWIM fluxgate design allows for more future applications in a variety of environments without sacrificing the performance seen on the MAGIC sensors. The UI team is looking forward to multiple upcoming flight opportunities for SWIM, including on the Observing Cusp High-altitude Reconnection and ElectroDynamics (OCHRE) and ICISbis sounding rockets.

Project Lead(s): Dr. David Miles, University of Iowa
Sponsoring Organization(s): Heliophysics Strategic Technology Office (HESTO)
 Article originally published at science.nasa.gov/technology

SWIM sensor magnetic calibration at NASA's GSFC.

The Heliophysics Technology Program plays a critical role in advancing Heliophysics Science. Some of these technologies are highlighted in NASA's Science Mission Directorate (SMD) Highlights.

A New Hybrid System Could Enable Spacecraft Attitude Control Systems to Perform Scientific Measurements

A NASA-sponsored team is creating a new approach to measure magnetic fields by developing a new system that can both take scientific measurements and provide spacecraft attitude control functions. This new system is small, lightweight, and can be accommodated onboard the spacecraft, eliminating the need for the boom structure that is typically required to measure Earth's magnetic field, thus allowing smaller, lower-cost spacecraft to take these measurements. In fact, this new system could not only enable small spacecraft to measure the magnetic field, it could replace the standard attitude control systems in future spacecraft that orbit Earth, allowing them to provide the important global measurements that enable us to understand how Earth's magnetic field protects us from dangerous solar particles.

Photo of the aurora (taken in Alaska) showing small scale features that are often present. Credit: NASA/Sebastian Saarloos

Solar storms drive space weather that threatens our many assets in space and can also disrupt Earth's upper atmosphere impacting our communications and power grids. Thankfully, the Earth's magnetic field protects us and funnels much of that energy into the north and south poles creating aurorae. The aurorae are a beautiful display of the electromagnetic energy and currents that flow throughout the Earth's space environment. They often have small-scale magnetic features that affect the total energy flowing through the system. Observing these small features requires multiple simultaneous observations over a broad range of spatial and temporal scales, which can be accomplished by constellations of small spacecraft.

To enable such constellations, NASA is developing an innovative hybrid magnetometer that makes both direct current (DC) and alternating current (AC) magnetic measurements and is embedded in the spacecraft's attitude determination and control system (ADCS)—the system that enables the satellite to know and control where it is pointing. High-performance, low SWAP+C (low-size, weight and power + cost) instruments are required, as is the ability to manufacture and test large numbers of these instruments within a typical flight build schedule. Future commercial or scientific satellites could use these small, lightweight embedded hybrid magnetometers to take the types of measurements that will expand our understanding of space weather and how Earth's magnetic field responds to solar storms.

It is typically not possible to take research-quality DC and AC magnetic measurements using sensors within an ADCS since the ADCS is inside the spacecraft and near contaminating sources of magnetic noise such as magnetic torque rods—the electromagnets that generate a magnetic field and push against the Earth's magnetic field to control the orientation of a spacecraft. Previous missions that have flown both DC and AC magnetometers placed them on long booms and each other as possible. In addition, the typical magnetometer used by an ADCS to measure the orientation of the spacecraft with respect to the geomagnetic field does not sample fast enough to measure the high-frequency signals needed to make magnetic field observations. A NASA-sponsored team at the University of Michigan is developing a new hybrid magnetometer and attitude determination and control system (HyMag-ADCS) that is a low-SWAP single package that can be integrated into a spacecraft without booms. HyMag-ADCS consists of a three-axis search coil AC magnetometer and a three-axis Quad-Mag DC magnetometer. The Quad-Mag DC magnetometer uses machine learning to enable boomless DC magnetometry, and the hybrid search-coil AC magnetometer includes attitude determination torque rods to enable the single 1U volume (103 cm) system to perform ADCS functions as well as collect science measurements.

The magnetic torque rod and search coil sensor (left) and the Quad-Mag magnetometer prototype (right). Image Credit: Mark Moldwin

The HyMag-ADCS team is incorporating the following technologies into the system to ensure success.

Quad-Mag Hardware: The Quad-Mag DC magnetometer consists of four magneto-inductive magnetometers and a space-qualified micro-controller mounted on a single CubeSat form factor (10 x 10 cm) printed circuit board. These two types of devices are commercially available. Combining multiple sensors on a single board increases the instrument's sensitivity by a factor of two compared to using a single sensor. In addition, the distributed sensors enable noise identification on small satellites, providing the science-grade magnetometer sensing that is key for both magnetic field measurements and attitude determination. The same type of magnetometer is part of the NASA Artemis Lunar Gateway Heliophysics Environmental and Radiation Measurement Experiment Suite (HERMES) Noisy Environment Magnetometer in a Small Integrated System (NEMISIS) magnetometer scheduled for launch in early 2027.

Dual-use Electromagnetic Rods: The HyMag-ADCS team is using search coil electronics and torque rod electronics that were developed for other efforts in a new way. Use of these two electronics systems enables the electromagnetic rods in the HyMag-ADCS system to be used in two different ways—as torque rods for attitude determination and as search coils to make scientific measurements. The search coil electronics were designed for ground-based measurements to observe ultra-low frequency signals up to a few kHz that are generated by magnetic beacons for indoor localization. The torque rod electronics were designed for use on CubeSats and have flown on several University of Michigan CubeSats (e.g., CubeSat-investigating Atmospheric Density Response to Extreme driving [CADRE]). The HyMag-ADCS concept is to use the torque rod electronics as needed for attitude control and use the search coil electronics the rest of the time to make scientific AC magnetic field measurements.

Early career electrical engineer Julio Vata and PhD student Jhanene Heying-Melendrez with art student resident Ana Trujillo Garcia in the magnetometer lab testing prototypes. Image Credit: Mark Moldwin

Machine Learning Algorithms for Spacecraft Noise Identification: Applying machine learning to these distributed sensors will autonomously remove noise generated by the spacecraft. The team is developing a powerful Unsupervised Blind Source Separation (UBSS) algorithm and a new method called Wavelet Adaptive Interference Cancellation for Underdetermined Platforms (WAIC-UP) to perform this task, and this method has already been demonstrated in simulation and the lab.

The HyMag-ADCS system is early in its development stage, and a complete engineering design unit is under development. The project is being completed primarily with undergraduate and graduate students, providing hands-on experiential training for upcoming scientists and engineers.

For additional details, see the entry for this project on NASA TechPort.

Project Lead: Prof. Mark Moldwin, University of Michigan
Sponsoring Organization: NASA Heliophysics Division's Heliophysics Technology and Instrument Development for Science (H-TIDeS) program
 Article originally published at science.nasa.gov/technology

SMD TECHNOLOGY HIGHLIGHTS

The Autonomous Ion Mass Spectrometer Sentry: Observing Ionospheric Plasma and Monitoring Contamination for the International Space Station

Figure 1. Planned location of the STP-H11 experiment pallet that will contain the Autonomous Ion Mass Spectrometer Sentry (AIMSS) on the International Space Station (Image courtesy of NASA).

Space weather describes the environmental conditions between Earth and the Sun, including particles, fields, and plasma that can affect assets in space and on Earth. Weather on Earth has many components including rain, temperature, extreme wind, ice, lightning, etc., and can be extreme. Weather in space is complicated because the environment consists of a complex collection of charged particles, sparse numbers of neutral molecules, along with ever-changing magnetic and electric fields. Satellites in space are subject to this extremely harsh environment, and space weather is studied in part because of the disruptions it can cause to electronics systems in space satellites.

A longstanding goal of the space weather community is to advance our capability to predict space weather events days in advance, in the same way that terrestrial weather forecasting enables one to anticipate a week of sunshine or snow. Improved space weather prediction could enable potential cost savings in areas such as spacecraft operations, aviation, and ground-based power grids.

One of the primary inhibitors to advancing our space weather forecasting capability is lack of knowledge and measurements of the constituent ion populations in space. There are two sources for ions in near-Earth space: the solar wind and the polar wind. The solar wind steadily emanates from the Sun and is composed of predominantly hydrogen, alpha particles, and high charge-state heavy ions. The polar wind emanates from Earth's upper atmosphere (the ionosphere) and is composed of singly ionized atoms and molecules including atomic hydrogen (H^+), atomic helium (He^+), and atomic oxygen (O^+) (see Figure 2 below), as well as atomic nitrogen (N^+), molecular nitrogen (N_2^+), molecular oxygen (O_2^+), and nitrogen oxide (NO^+). The process by which these low-energy ions leave Earth's atmosphere and enter near-Earth space is called ionospheric outflow and is an area of significant study.

Figure 2. Depiction of the ionospheric outflow, or polar wind, where singly charged ions follow magnetic field lines out into the magnetosphere. Courtesy of NASA and the European Space Agency.

due to their similar masses. Ambiguity between N^+ and O^+ is problematic, as measurements and models show that these ions behave differently in space due to differences in their upper atmospheric source (different scale heights and photoionization), transport (different behaviors in electric and magnetic fields), and loss mechanisms (e.g., neutralization via charge exchange with ambient neutral hydrogen, or geocoronal H_2). Our poor knowledge about the differences in source, transport, and loss of N^+ and O^+ in the space environment makes it impossible to validate modern space weather models and hinders our ability to predict space weather.

The Autonomous Ion Mass Spectrometer Sentry (AIMSS) is designed to make high mass resolution observations of the ionospheric plasma and to measure man-made contamination caused by the interaction of the ionospheric plasma with the thruster plumes from spacecraft delivering supplies and crew to the International Space Station (ISS). The particles expelled by these thruster systems contaminate space station surfaces, causing degradation of optical and thermal surfaces and resulting in increased charging of the spacecraft surface.

A team at Los Alamos National Laboratory is leveraging SMD-funded technology developments to design a novel sensor that examines the interactions between space plasma and the plumes generated by the thrusters of spacecraft delivering supplies and crew members to the International Space Station. Not only will this sensor monitor conditions at the space station, it will also provide information to enable more accurate space weather prediction for other locations in space.

AIMSS is also capable of distinguishing ions of ionospheric origin, including N^+ , O^+ , N_2^+ , O_2^+ , and NO^+ . As mentioned, most modern space plasma mass spectrometers are typically incapable of these measurements. Furthermore, AIMSS will measure these ionospheric ions and molecular ions from a pallet mounted onboard the space station, which resides in the Earth's ionosphere. The resulting measurements will provide important inputs and validation for space weather forecasting models. AIMSS will also serve as a testbed for future missions targeting cold magnetospheric plasma.

The AIMSS payload is a double focusing mass spectrometer and utilizes electric and magnetic field geometries to focus in both direction and energy. The AIMSS instrument design and operation are illustrated in Figure 3. This design allows for multiple ion species to become spatially distributed by mass-to-charge ratio (M/q) along the focal plane.

Specifically, lighter ions entering the analyzer will have a shorter path length than heavier ions, creating a series of concentric paths almost like a rainbow, as shown in Figure 3 (right). The instrument is comprised of: (1) a laminated collimator to set the field-of-view (FOV); (2) a laminated electrostatic analyzer (ESA) to selectively filter ions by the energy-to-charge ratio (E/q); (3) a magnetic sector analyzer (designed and built by Plasma Controls at Colorado State University) to separate ions by M/q ; and (4) a microchannel plate (MCP) followed by position sensitive cross delay anode (XDL) assembly to detect the location of the ions on the detector plane.

Figure 4: Modeled AIMSS instrument response with regard to mass resolution at various locations: (A) Earth, (B) Venus, (C) Jupiter, (D) Saturn, and (E) the pristine solar wind.

The ability of AIMSS to distinguish between ion populations found in various planetary ionospheres and regions of the solar system was modeled and is shown in Figure 4. Various ion species were modeled as they entered the instrument and travelled through the detector sections, shown in Figure 3, to be recorded as measured counts. The locations and species of the ions landing on the detection plane are shown in Figure 4 for a variety of possible locations: (A) Earth, (B) Venus, (C) Jupiter, (D) Saturn, and (E) the pristine solar wind (i.e., there is no interaction with a nearby planet). These end-to-end electro-optic modeling results indicate that the AIMSS detector can provide high mass resolution observations of planetary ionospheres critical for advancing space plasma science.

The NASA Heliophysics Technology and Instrument Development for Science (H-TiDeS) Program funded early AIMSS efforts to refine the design concept, conduct prototype testing of subsystems, and advance the technology readiness level (TRL). The instrument was subsequently proposed to, and selected by, the Los Alamos National Laboratory (LANL) Laboratory Directed Research and Development (LDRD) Program Office and is currently being built, tested, and calibrated at LANL. The payload containing AIMSS will fly on the Space Test Program – Houston 11 (STP-H11) mission to the International Space Station in early 2026. This flight will provide on-orbit data to validate the instrument performance and inform future design improvements for instruments destined for the magnetosphere.

Project Leads: Dr. Carlos A. Maldonado, Los Alamos National Laboratory (LANL), Dr. Matthew G. McHarg, United States Air Force Academy (USAF)

Sponsoring Organizations: NASA H-TiDeS and LANL Laboratory Directed Research and Development (LDRD) Program Office, DoD Space Test Program

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Innovative Instrument Reveals Hidden Features Deep Inside the Van Allen Radiation Belts

A new instrument is using advanced detection techniques and leveraging an orbit with specific characteristics to increase our understanding of the Van Allen belts—regions surrounding Earth that contain energetic particles that can endanger both robotic and human space missions. Recently, the instrument provided a unique view of changes to this region that were brought on by an intense magnetic storm in May 2024.

The discovery of the Van Allen radiation belts by the U.S. Explorer 1 mission in 1958 marked a prominent milestone in space physics and demonstrated that Earth's magnetosphere efficiently accelerates and traps energetic particles. The inner belt contains protons in the MeV (million electric volt) to GeV (10⁹ electric volt) range, and even higher concentrations of energetic electrons of 100s of keV (1000 electric volt) to MeV are found in both the inner belt and the outer belt.

The energetic electrons in these belts—also referred to as “killer electrons”—can have detrimental effects on spacecraft subsystems and are harmful to astronauts performing extravehicular activities. Understanding the source, loss, and varying concentrations of these electrons has been a longstanding research objective. High-energy resolution and clean measurements of these energetic electrons in space are required to further our understanding of their properties and enable more reliable prediction of their intensity.

Overcoming the challenges of measuring relativistic electrons in the inner belt

Measuring energetic electrons cleanly and accurately has been a challenge, especially in the inner belt, where MeV to GeV energy protons also exist. NASA's Van Allen Probes, which operated from 2012 to 2019 in low inclination, geo-transfer-like orbits, showed that instruments traversing the heart of the inner radiation belt are subject to penetration by the highly energetic protons located in that region. The Relativistic Electron Proton Telescope (REPT) and the Magnetic Electron Ion Spectrometer (MagEIS) instruments onboard the Van Allen Probes were heavily shielded but were still subject to inner-belt proton contamination.

To attempt to minimize these negative effects, a University of Colorado Boulder team led by Dr. Xinlin Li, designed the Relativistic Electron Proton Telescope integrated little experiment (REPTile)—a simplified and miniaturized version of REPT—to fly onboard the Colorado Student Space Weather Experiment (CSSWE). An effort supported by the National Science Foundation, the 3-Unit CSSWE CubeSat operated in a highly inclined low Earth orbit (LEO) from 2012 to 2014. In this highly inclined orbit, the spacecraft and the instruments it carried were only exposed to the inner-belt protons in the South Atlantic Anomaly (SAA) region where the Earth's magnetic field is weaker, which greatly reduced the time that protons impacted the measurement of electrons.

REPTile's success motivated a team, also led by Dr. Xinlin Li, to design REPTile-2—an advanced version of REPTile—to be hosted on the Colorado Inner Radiation Belt Experiment (CIRBE) mission. Like CSSWE, CIRBE operates in a highly inclined low-Earth orbit to ensure the exposure to damaging inner-belt protons is minimized. The team based the REPTile-2 design on REPTile but incorporated two additional technologies—guard rings and Pulse Height Analysis—to enable clean, high-energy-resolution measurements of energetic electrons, especially in the inner belt.

Figure 3. Left (adapted from Figure 1 of Khoo et al., 2022): Illustration of REPTile-2 front end with key features labeled; Right: REPTile-2 front end integrated with electronic boards and structures, a computer-aided design (CAD) model, and a photo of integrated REPTile-2. Image Credit: Xinlin Li, UC Boulder

Figure 1. An artist's concept of the Van Allen belts with a cutaway section of the giant donuts of radiation that surround Earth. Image Credit: NASA's GSFC/SVS

As shown on the left in Figure 3, the field of view (FOV) of REPTile-2 is 51°. Electrons and protons enter the FOV and are measured when they reach a stack of silicon detectors where they deposit their energies. However, very energetic protons (energy greater than 60 MeV) could penetrate through the instrument's tungsten and aluminum shielding and masquerade as valid particles, thus contaminating the intended measurements. To mitigate this contamination, the team designed guard rings that surround each detector. These guard rings are electronically separated from the inner active area of each detector and are connected by a separate electric channel. When the guard rings are triggered (i.e., hit by particles coming outside of the FOV), the coincident measurements are considered invalid and are discarded. This anti-coincidence technique enables cleaner measurements of particles coming through the FOV.

To achieve high energy resolution, the team also applied full Pulse Height Analysis (PHA) on REPTile-2. In PHA, the magnitude of measured charge in the detector is directly proportional to the energy deposited from the incident electrons. Unlike REPTile, which employed a simpler energy threshold discrimination method yielding three channels for the electrons, REPTile-2 offers enhanced precision with 60 energy channels for electron energies ranging from 0.25 – 6 MeV. The REPT instrument onboard the Van Allen Probes also employed PHA but while REPT worked very well in the outer belt, yielding fine energy resolution, it did not function as well in the inner belt since the instrument was fully exposed to penetrating energetic protons because it did not have the guard rings implemented.

CIRBE and REPTile-2 Results

CIRBE's launch, secured through the NASA CubeSat Launch Initiative (CSLI), took place aboard SpaceX's Falcon 9 rocket as part of the Transporter-7 mission on April 15, 2023. REPTile-2, activated on April 19, 2023, has been performing well, delivering valuable data about Earth's radiation belt electrons. Many features of the energetic electrons in the Van Allen belts have been revealed for the first time, thanks to the high-resolution energy and time measurements REPTile-2 has provided.

Figure 5 shows a sample of CIRBE/REPTile-2 measurements from April 2024, and illustrates the intricate drift echoes or “zebra stripes” of energetic electrons, swirling around Earth in distinct bunches. These observations span a vast range across the inner and outer belts, encompassing a wide spectrum of energies and electron fluxes extending over six orders of magnitude. By leveraging advanced guard rings, Pulse Height Analysis (PHA), and a highly inclined LEO orbit, REPTile-2 is delivering unprecedented observations of radiation belt electrons. In fact, the team recently announced that measurements from CIRBE/REPTile-2 have revealed a new temporary third radiation belt composed of electrons and sandwiched between the two permanent belts. This belt formed during the magnetic storm in May 2024, which was the largest in two decades. While such temporary belts have been seen after big storms previously, the data from CIRBE/REPTile-2 are providing a new viewpoint with higher energy resolution data than before. Scientists are currently studying the data to better understand the belt and how long it might stick around—which could be many months.

Project Lead: Dr. Xinlin Li, University of Colorado Laboratory for Atmospheric and Space Physics and Department of Aerospace Engineering Sciences

Sponsoring Organizations: Heliophysics Flight Opportunities for Research & Technology (H-FORT) program, National Science Foundation

Article originally published at science.nasa.gov/technology

Figure 5: Color-coded electron fluxes detrended between REPTile-2 measurements for a pass over the South Atlantic Anomaly region on April 24, 2023, and their average, i.e., the smoothed electron fluxes using a moving average window of $\pm 19\%$ in energy; Black curves plotted on top of the color-coded electron fluxes are contours of electron drift period in hr. The second horizontal-axis, L , represents the magnetic field line, which CIRBE crosses. The two radiation belts and a slot region in between are indicated by the red lines and arrow, respectively. Image Credit: Xinlin Li, UC Boulder

SMD TECHNOLOGY HIGHLIGHTS

Making Ultra-fast Electron Measurements in Multiple Directions to Reveal the Secrets of the Aurora

Photo of the aurora (taken in Greenland) that shows tall rays extending to high altitudes. These rays are caused by particles, mainly electrons and protons, precipitating into the upper atmosphere from space. Image Credit: NASA-GSFC

The energetic electrons that drive the aurora borealis (the northern lights) have a rich and very dynamic structure that we currently do not fully understand. Much of what we know about these electrons comes from instruments that have fundamental limitations in their ability to sample multiple energies with high time resolution. To overcome these limitations, NASA is using an innovative approach to develop instrumentation that will enhance our measurement capabilities by more than an order of magnitude—revealing a wealth of new information about the amazing physics happening within the aurora.

Team members Albert Risco Patino and Ellen Robertson assembling an electronics stack for an APES instrument to go on a sounding rocket. Image Credit: NASA's GSFC

Typical electron instruments rely on a technique called electrostatic deflection, which requires changing a voltage to select different energies of electrons to measure. These instruments have been flown on many different space missions and have provided almost all of the *in situ* electron measurements made inside the aurora. They work great when observing on timescales of seconds or even down to around a tenth of a second, but they fundamentally cannot observe down to smaller (millisecond) timescales due to the time it takes to sweep through voltages.

Ground-based optical observations of the aurora have shown that there can be rapid spatial and temporal variations that are beyond the observing capabilities of traditional electron instruments. Therefore, members of the Geophysics Laboratory at NASA's Goddard Space Flight

Precipitating electron spectra measured inside the aurora at one millisecond time resolution using the APES instrument on the Visualizing Ion Outflow via Neutral Atom Sensing-2 (VISIONS-2) sounding rocket flight. This entire plot covers a period of 300 milliseconds. The slanted red stripes in the middle of the figure are on the order of 10 milliseconds apart. Image Credit: NASA's GSFC

Center developed an instrument called the Acute Precipitating Electron Spectrometer (APES) that can measure electron precipitation within the aurora at a one millisecond cadence. APES uses a strong magnetic field inside the instrument to separate electrons with different energies onto different spatial regions of the detector. This method allows the instrument to measure the entire electron energy spectrum simultaneously at a very high rate (every 1 ms).

In the design of APES, one major trade-off had to be made. For the magnetic field geometry to work properly, the instrument can only observe in one direction. This concept works

well if the goal is just to measure the precipitating (downgoing) electrons in the aurora that ultimately hit the atmosphere. However, we know that electrons in the aurora also move in other directions; in fact, these electrons contain a lot of information about other physical processes happening farther out in space.

To enable measurement of electrons in more than one direction, the Goddard team developed the APES-360 instrument concept. To create the APES-360 design, the team employed the same operating principles used in APES, but updated them to accommodate a multi-look direction geometry that covers a 360-degree field of view using 16 different sectors. The team had to overcome several technical challenges to develop the APES-360 concept. In particular, the electronics design had to accommodate many more anodes (charge detecting surfaces) and the associated circuitry in a small area.

The APES-360 prototype that is currently being built will be tested and calibrated at Goddard and will fly on a sounding rocket into active aurora in the winter of 2025. This flight will provide real-life data from inside the aurora that will be used to validate the instrument performance and inform future design improvements.

The APES-360 instrument is being designed to fit into a CubeSat form factor so that it can be used on future CubeSat missions to study the aurora. The instrument could also ultimately be flown on larger orbital missions, as well.

Project Lead: Dr. Robert G Michell, NASA Goddard Space Flight Center (GSFC)
Sponsoring Organizations: Heliophysics, Geospace Physics Laboratory (GSFC Code 673) and H-TIDEs

Article originally published at science.nasa.gov/technology

The design of the mechanical assembly of the magnetic optics section for APES-360. The actual magnets are the orange rectangles near the middle. The entrance aperture is a gap between the green and red outer bands. Image Credit: NASA's GSFC

Magnet assembly of prototype APES-360 instrument for simultaneously measuring electron spectra in 16 different directions. Image Credit: NASA's GSFC

AGU: Heliophysics at American Geophysical Union

The American Geophysical Union (AGU) meeting took place this year in New Orleans, Louisiana from Dec 15-18. The AGU Fall meeting is the largest gathering of Earth and space scientists – historically more than 25,000 attendees from over 100 countries attend this meeting. AGU is a major enabler for scientific exchange, knowledge dissemination, and community building. Many of our technologists attended in person and presented their work in posters and talks in sessions, including To the Moon: A New Era of Lunar Science; Understanding Space Weather for Human and Robotic Exploration to the Moon, Mars, and Beyond; Space Plasma Physics Instrumentation and Measurement Techniques; High-Energy Heliophysics Science and the Engineering Realities to Make It Possible; and Machine Learning in Space Weather and Heliophysics. HESTO Lead Scientist Steven Christe attended, meeting with many of our technologists in person to discuss their latest developments and facilitate collaboration.

HESTO Lead Scientist Steven Christe at AGU25.

Olivia Jones during poster session Fluxgate Magnetometers New Core Material Experimentation and Performance.

Andrew Nicholas and Reinhard Friedel presenting on Lightsheet Anomaly Resolution and Debris Observation (LARADO).

Amy Gall taking questions after her session Laboratory Spectroscopy of Fe Ions: Supporting Next Generation Solar Missions.

Dhiren Kataria presenting A High Geometric Factor Spectrometer for Fast Plasma Measurements on Future Missions.

Tithi Patel during poster session Pushing CubeSat Limits to Investigate High-Energy Electron Acceleration.

Joe Westlake, Director of the NASA Science Mission Directorate's Heliophysics Division, presenting on the future of Heliophysics.

Georgia de Nolfo, Lucas Cunningham, & Grant Mitchell during poster session SONTRAC Neutron Path Reconstruction, Physics-Informed Machine Learning.

Amir Caspi and Drew Turner presenting on Development of the Suprathermal Particle and Relativistic Electron Magnetic Spectrometer (SuPREMeS).

EMERGING TECHNOLOGY

The future of Heliophysics demands a paradigm shift in how we develop technology. As the US looks toward the next decade and beyond, NASA's goal is to accelerate the cadence of science through leaner, faster, and more efficient mission architectures.

Alexander Barrie
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Enabling Responsive Autonomous Onboard Operations with MEDOS

What if you could effectively put the operations team on the spacecraft? The Module for Events Driven Operations on Spacecraft (MEDOS) is an onboard operations agent that does just that. Typical mission operations require predicting when and where an event may occur, often requiring commands to be scheduled up to weeks in advance.

However, space is a highly dynamic environment primarily driven by solar activity. For example, spacecraft in Earth orbit may cross environmental boundaries that require a change in operational mode. What if we could detect and respond to space weather changes in real-time to ensure the safety of our spacecraft and astronauts for NASA's Moon to Mars initiative?

MEDOS is a software agent that analyzes on-board measurements to generate real-time operational decisions. This next-generation operations agent will enable the missions fulfilling NASA's exploration goals to operate autonomously and respond to changing environments when real-time ground intervention is not possible such as when astronauts are on the Martian surface or in deep space. It leverages fuzzy logic to calculate a confidence level for a specific event and uses this to generate operational decisions. Through this approach, MEDOS is computationally lightweight, fully explainable, and runs within existing flight software systems (CFS, F Prime, etc.). MEDOS was demonstrated in flight on NASA's Magnetospheric Multiscale (MMS) mission, bringing it to TRL 7.

More information about MEDOS is available at:
<https://ntrs.nasa.gov/citations/20250002215>.

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Teaching Physics to Machine Learning to Protect Astronauts from Radiation

Solar neutron radiation is a challenge for spacecraft and astronaut safety, particularly for missions beyond Earth's atmosphere. Neutrons interact only weakly with materials, making them difficult to detect. The SOLar Neutron TRACKing (SONTRAC) instrument is designed to measure the energy and direction of these incoming solar neutrons. When a neutron passes through SONTRAC, it can collide with a proton inside a scintillating fiber, producing ionization and subsequent scintillation along its path, tracking the proton's motion. The SONTRAC team trained a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) on simulated data to predict proton paths from registered fibers in the bundle. Although CNN produced realistic proton tracks, the resulting neutron reconstructions were sometimes physically impossible. To remedy this, the team improved the model's loss function—the metric guiding how a machine-learning model learns. Instead of evaluating only proton-track accuracy, the new loss function also checks whether a reconstructed neutron obeys basic physical kinematic constraints. This “physics-informed” approach dramatically reduced unphysical predictions, creating a more reliable model. Such techniques show strong promise for future NASA missions, including for Moon to Mars, where autonomous, physics-aware AI could help assess radiation risk in real time. Similar approaches could also enhance medical imaging, materials testing, and other applications that rely on reconstruction guided by constraints of physical processes.

University of New Hampshire

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AI-Enabled Spacecraft Attitude Control Systems That Perform Science Measurements

A UM team is advancing space-based magnetic field measurements with Hybrid AC/DC Magnetometer with Attitude Determination and Control System (HyMag-ADCS), an innovative hybrid system that uses AI and machine learning (AI/ML) to enable boomless magnetometry. Traditional spacecraft require booms to separate sensitive magnetometers from spacecraft noise sources, limiting deployment on cost-effective smallsats.

The breakthrough lies in advanced AI/ML algorithms that autonomously identify and remove spacecraft-generated magnetic interference. HyMag-ADCS employs Unsupervised Blind Source Separation (UBSS) and a novel Wavelet Adaptive Interference Cancellation for Underdetermined Platforms (WAIC-UP) technique to deliver research-quality measurements from sensors embedded into a spacecraft's attitude control system.

This dual-purpose 1U (103 cm) system combines a Quad-Mag DC magnetometer with distributed sensors and electromagnetic rods that function as attitude control torque rods and scientific research coils. AI/ML algorithms double sensitivity while enabling study of small-scale space weather features.

This innovation, will enable affordable smallsat constellations that provide critical global magnetic field observations and advances our understanding of how Earth's magnetosphere protects us from solar particles and space weather threats. Supporting NASA's Moon to Mars initiative, this type of magnetometer is integrated into the Artemis Lunar Gateway HERMES suite scheduled for launch in 2027.

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HERT: A Miniaturized Telescope for Resolving Radiation Belt Acceleration Mechanisms

Earth's radiation belts contain relativistic electrons with energies in the MeV energy range and above. These highly energetic particles pose serious risk to spacecraft and humans, so understanding these electrons is critical to mitigating radiation hazards.

The miniaturized High-Energy-Resolution relativistic electron Telescope (HERT), designed for a cubesat mission in geosynchronous transfer orbit, will address key radiation belt research challenges. HERT measures high-energy-resolution 1–7 MeV electrons, distinguishing between competing acceleration mechanisms in Earth's radiation belts. Such insights are essential to improving space weather models and ensuring mission safety beyond Earth.

A HERT major innovation is the use of a machine learning algorithm to classify particle species with >98% accuracy. By embedding the model in the flight software, it achieves autonomous, accurate particle classification suitable to a resource-constrained cubesat. HERT also applies the generalized least squares method to reconstruct particle flux from count rate measurements, enhancing accuracy and energy resolution. It has demonstrated 50+ krad radiation tolerance and the team will validate its high-energy-resolution performance in beam testing.

HERT advances the fidelity of radiation environment characterization, supporting NASA's Moon to Mars objectives by enabling high-resolution radiation monitoring and setting the stage for next-generation space weather instruments that will safeguard humanity's journey deeper into the solar system.

AUBURN UNIVERSITY

LASP

PATHFINDER

BRIDGING THE GAP FROM CONCEPT TO FLIGHT

Miniaturized Double Langmuir Probe Enables Smallsat Measurements

The miniaturized Double Langmuir Probe (mDLP) team at Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University (ERAU) is working to develop a compact, lightweight Langmuir probe capable of measuring plasma temperature and density from small satellites or rocket platforms.

Langmuir probes analyze plasma by measuring electrical current at differing bias voltages. Traditional probes work well on large spacecraft, but cubesats face a critical challenge: their small conductive surface area causes the spacecraft to charge unpredictably when the probe sweeps through voltages, making accurate electron temperature measurements difficult. Although existing miniaturized non-sweeping probes can measure plasma density, temperature measurements have remained elusive on these small platforms. The proposed mDLP instrument uses a novel double Langmuir probe design to overcome this limitation, enabling both high-rate density and temperature measurements from small satellites or rocket platforms.

This instrument development is crucial to conducting affordable, low resource, low impact Langmuir probe measurements. A rideshare opportunity on the Resolute sounding rocket mission in 2027 will enable *in situ* testing of the developed instrument, in addition to providing science data useful to the Resolute campaign. mDLP's measurements will support and be cross-validated by heritage instruments integrated into the Resolute main payload. These instruments will provide independent verification of the mitigated spacecraft charging provided by this new Langmuir probe.

Launching 2027

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Resolute Mission PI: Glyn Collinson, NASA's GSFC

HESTO Pathfinder plays a critical role in ushering Heliophysics technologies across the gap from early development into flight readiness. Building on advancements made through NASA's Heliophysics Technology and Instrument Development for Science (H-TIDS) program, Pathfinder provides a structured pathway for instruments and technologies to progress beyond the proof-of-concept stage, maturing technologies for infusion into larger missions, such as Explorers. Pathfinder funding is currently awarded to PIs who have secured their own rideshare opportunities, which focuses funding on technology maturation vs flight costs. By promoting technology flight demonstration through rideshare access, Pathfinder leverages validation of highly promising technologies in relevant operational environments, maximizing the potential for successfully infusing technologies into future Heliophysics missions.

Thermo5D on Dynamo-3: Flight Testing a New Space Weather Instrument

The new Thermo5D instrument is scheduled to be flight-tested in August 2026 on a pair of sounding rockets that comprise the Dynamo-3 investigation.

Thermo5D will return measurements of five parameters that indicate the state of the gas comprising the upper atmosphere: density, three dimensional wind vectors, and temperature. These parameters are the primary elements of the weather in the thermosphere. Of these, density is considered the most important parameter, as it plays a large role in the orbital evolution of satellites. Particularly in this area of space, it adds substantial drag on orbiting spacecraft. Winds and temperature are important determinants of how weather changes and are used to inform space weather models.

The Dynamo-3 investigation seeks to understand how the state of the thermosphere works with the plasma and electric fields of the commingled ionosphere to produce the daytime ionospheric dynamo. It will evaluate the terms in the local atmospheric dynamo equation for consistency as a test of our understanding of dynamo physics. The thermospheric density and winds measured by Thermo5D are important quantities in making this determination. Dynamo-3 is an ideal project for testing Thermo5D, as the rocket's other payloads are larger instruments making the same measurements, providing a control against which Thermo5D measurements can be compared.

Launching 2026

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Dynamo-3 Mission PI: Robert Pfaff, NASA's GSFC

Assistance: A Machine Learning-enabled Boomless Rocket Magnetometer

The Assistance magnetometer on the Resolute rocket mission will demonstrate new machine learning (ML) algorithms designed to remove rocket and instrument noise from a body-mounted magnetometer. The Assistance magnetometer takes the name of HMS Assistance, a sister Arctic exploration ship to HMS Resolute that searched for Captain Franklin and his lost crew 175 years ago.

This instrument enables crucial space environment technology development for a new boomless magnetometer, provides rocket magnetic noise identification, supplies redundancy to the fluxgate magnetometers, mitigates risk of boom deployment misalignment and failure, and contributes to the mission's science investigations. Assistance will support understanding estimates of electromagnetic energy flux and field-aligned currents (FAC), enabling calibrated and clean magnetometer observations at the smallest scales possible.

Assistance is an innovative instrument consisting of four Positioning Navigation Intelligence (PNI) RM3100 magneto-inductive magnetometers and a space-qualified micro-controller (TI MSP430) on a single 10x10-cm printed circuit board. By combining multiple sensors on a single board, the Assistance team increased its sensitivity by a factor of two compared to a single instrument. In addition, the distributed sensors enable noise identification on small satellites and rockets, providing science-grade magnetometer sensing key to both magnetic field measurements.

Launching 2027

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Resolute Mission PI: Glyn Collinson, NASA's GSFC

MOON TO MARS: HELIOPHYSICS TECHNOLOGY ENABLES REACHING THE NEW FRONTIER

The goal of the Heliophysics Technology Program (HTP) is to push the boundaries of what is conceivable and achievable today. Human and robotic exploration to the Moon, Mars, and beyond creates new challenges for ensuring crew safety, spacecraft survivability, and operational reliability. NASA's Moon to Mars architecture relies on our ability to understand, predict, and operate outside the protections of Earth's magnetic field. Beyond Earth, the space radiation environment – particularly solar energetic particles (SEPs) and coronal mass ejections (CMEs) – presents a hazard to crews and equipment. The Heliophysics Division (HPD) is rising to the challenge of developing the unique capabilities needed to close measurement gaps that advance space weather forecasting and scientific discovery. The HPD Technology Program is essential to enabling rapid and reliable production of advanced capabilities, catalyzing the technological advancements needed to explore Moon, Mars, and beyond.

Processes originating at the Sun impact human activities on and near the Moon, in deep space transit, and on and near Mars.

Lunar Neutron Monitor

- Monitors neutron environment
- Provides missing radiation dose contribution for astronaut health and safety
- Models SEP impacts on lunar surface

Transit SEP Detector

- Provides real-time SEP/dose measurements
- Supplies 'seek shelter' warnings to astronauts
- Probes SEP angular and radial extent

Lunar Dust Monitor

- Monitors dust that damages equipment and poses health risks to astronauts
- Provides safety insights into dust transport mechanisms, electrostatic levitation, micrometer impacts/ejecta plumes

Mars Magnetograph

- Monitors the Sun's magnetic field facing Mars to predict potential solar events (CMEs, solar flares)
- Constrains magnetic models of the Sun by enabling 360° coverage combined with data from Earth/L4/L5

Transit Plasma Analyzer

- Monitors solar wind speed, density, and temperature
- Detects changes caused by solar events
- Constrains solar wind propagation models

Mars Visible Light Coronagraph

- Monitors CMEs headed toward Mars and provides space weather alerts
- Constrains CME structure and speed combined with data from Earth and L1

Mars X-ray Imager

- Provides input to predictive SEP models
- Constrains the particle acceleration process in solar flares combined with data from Earth

Mars High-Performance Computer System

- Synthesizes Mars sensor data
- Runs AI/ML models to provide forecasting/nowcasting of space weather activity

Heliophysics Environmental and Radiation Measurement Experiment Suite (HERMES)

Real-time energetic ion and electron (e.g., SEP) monitoring will enable deep-space and long-term human exploration. HERMES, a planned Lunar Gateway payload, is funded by NASA's Space Weather Program. It is a pathfinder project, pioneering hybrid instruments with operational goals. HERMES' four instruments will measure *in situ* energetic particles and magnetic fields. With other Gateway instruments, HERMES measures astronauts' radiation exposure inside and outside the spacecraft. HTP investments directly led to advancing at least two HERMES instruments.

Escape and Plasma Acceleration and Dynamics Explorers (ESCAPADE)

ESCAPADE, a Heliophysics-funded Mars mission launched in 2025, will arrive at Mars in September 2027. Its two spacecraft will study the interaction between the solar wind and the Martian atmosphere, as well as the local Martian magnetosphere, by measuring energetic particles and magnetic fields to understand how the solar wind drives atmospheric loss. ESCAPADE is the first Heliophysics mission to Mars, a pathfinder for future Heliophysics instruments on or near Mars.

NASA's Lunar Gateway: humanity's outpost orbiting the Moon

Monitoring Mars to enable future human habitation

INFUSION HIGHLIGHTS

ELP: Instrument Development Investments Enabling NASA Moon To Mars Goals

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12-LCAS12-0015, 16-HTIDS16_2-0024, 18-HTIDS18_2-0030, 17-SIMPLEX18-0005

The Space and Atmospheric Instrumentation Lab (SAIL) at Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University (ERAU) has been developing low size, weight, and power (SWaP) Langmuir probe instruments to support multi-point measurements in sub-orbital and orbital missions since 2009. Originally funded through a Florida Space Grant Consortium grant, SAIL developed a fixed-bias multi-metal Langmuir probe that was flown on the German WAVE Driven In-situ Studies (WADIS) I and II sounding rockets.

SAIL's initial success led to a Heliophysics Low Cost Access to Space (H-LCAS) proposal that enabled a suite of fixed-bias—and now sweep-bias—Langmuir probes flown on the Mesosphere-Lower Thermosphere Turbulence Experiment (MTeX) sounding rocket. A Heliophysics Flight Opportunities for Research and Technology (HFORT) project in 2017 further enabled development of a miniaturized Planar Ion Probe that was flown on the Low-Latitude Ionosphere/Thermosphere Enhancements in Density (LLITED) mission. This work then fed into a subsequent 2019 LCAS project, as well as a funded proposal to the NASA Small Innovative Missions for Planetary Exploration (SimpleX) program.

ELP in the RocketLab integration facility.

This work laid the foundation for SAIL's development of the radiation-tolerant, miniaturized ESCAPEDE Langmuir Probe (ELP) for the Escape and Plasma Acceleration and Dynamics Explorers (ESCAPEDE) mission. ESCAPEDE/ELP launched November 13, 2025, from Cape Canaveral Space Force Station, Florida, and is currently on its way to Mars. ELP will measure thermal plasma density in the Martian ionosphere across the altitude range of 150 to 1000 km.

This instrument, with its exceptionally low SWaP profile—weighing less than 600 grams, consuming less than 1 Watt of power, and demonstrating radiation tolerance up to 25 krad—exemplifies cutting-edge Heliophysics design supporting planetary missions. The ELP instrument suite comprises four fixed bias needles in the electron saturation region, two planar probes biased in the ion saturation region, and a sphere used as a floating potential probe to assess relative changes in spacecraft charging. The ELP thermal plasma density measurement range is 100 to 50,000 cm⁻³, and the relative charging measurement range is ±12 V.

ELP shows how continuous and iterative instrument development, investment, and flight testing enable innovative missions like ESCAPEDE to realize NASA's Moon to Mars goals.

ELP printed circuit board.

ELP PI Aroh Barjatya and HESTO Lead Roshanak Hakimzadeh inspecting the ELP Langmuir probe prior to ESCAPEDE satellite encapsulation on Blue Origin's New Glenn 2.

ESCAPEDE satellites.

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Reviving Lost Technology: MAGIC Fluxgate Magnetometers on TRACERS

Space-based magnetic field measurements are crucial to understanding Earth's magnetosphere and solar wind interactions, space weather forecasting, and planetary exploration. The MAGnetometers for Innovation and Capability (MAGIC) technology demonstration revives a nearly lost art in fluxgate magnetometers, which make precise magnetic field measurements using a tiny ferromagnetic core to modulate the local magnetic field. The fluxgate magnetometer core technology, originally adapted from naval applications, vanished after the Cold War. Production of key fluxgate ring-cores halted, leaving missions reliant on dwindling stockpiles. MAGIC changed this by flight demonstrating new fluxgate cores, ensuring reliable, high-performance sensors for future endeavors.

MAGIC is hosted on NASA's Tandem Reconnection and Cusp Electrodynamic Reconnaissance Satellites (TRACERS), a Small Explorers (SMEX) mission. TRACERS probes the dynamic process of magnetic reconnection in Earth's dayside magnetosphere, using two spacecraft. One hosts MAGIC with backward-compatible ring-cores for integration into existing designs and the other features the new racetrack geometry cores that enable ultra-stable sensors.

Building on this success, Space Weather Iowa Magnetometer (SWIM) provides a compact, low-resource design with nanosatellite-scale electronics and digital feedback for enhanced stability. SWIM's low-field mode is ideal for monitoring solar wind and planetary environments, supporting NASA's Moon to Mars initiative by enabling measurements in the Moon's weak crustal fields and Mars' thin atmosphere. SWIM is suitable for crewed mission space weather forecasting, safeguarding astronauts from radiation hazards. SWIM will undergo test flights on the ICI-5b suborbital rocket in March 2026 and OCHRE rocket in 2027, paving the way for infusion into space weather networks and deep-space exploration.

MAGIC on TRACERS.

Launched July 2025

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IOWA

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REAL: High Resolution Measurements in the Near-Earth Radiation Environment

In 2025, the Relativistic Electron Atmospheric Loss (REAL) cubesat was launched into a low-Earth sun synchronous polar orbit as a rideshare on Tandem Reconnection and Cusp Electrodynamic Reconnaissance Satellites (TRACERS). REAL is answering critically important questions about the near-Earth radiation environment. The three-axis stabilized 3U cubesat measures electrons raining down on Earth's atmosphere from the radiation belts to better understand radiation belt electron loss processes. REAL quantifies radiation belt electron loss rates, identifies where and when different electron loss modes are important, and advances our understanding of plasma wave-particle interactions in space plasmas.

To address its objectives, REAL makes high time-resolution measurements of electron angular distributions, essential for understanding the physics of the scattering process. The measurements are enabled by a new multi-aperture particle instrument, flying for the first time on REAL. Previous measurements of the electron angular distribution were made from a spinning spacecraft, limiting the time cadence to a few seconds. REAL's novel aperture design enables simultaneous observations every 20 ms in multiple look directions relative to the magnetic field. These high time cadence measurements are necessary to understand rapid electron microbursts – one of the primary loss processes for radiation belt electrons. REAL measures electrons over a wide energy range (1 keV to 2 MeV) with excellent energy resolution.

The REAL mission is the first flight of this instrument design, raising the TRL of a new particle detection capability. A follow-on instrument was recently developed for an operational mission, and the instrument will also be adapted for the next Heliophysics Small Explorer mission, Cross-scale Investigation of Earth's Magnetotail and Aurora (CINEMA), to study the dynamics of Earth's magnetosphere.

Launch-ready REAL spacecraft showing the REAL instrument.

Launched July 2025

TRACERS PI: David Miles,
The University of Iowa

DARTMOUTH

MONTANA STATE UNIVERSITY

APL JOHN'S HOPKINS APPLIED PHYSICS LABORATORY

BOSTON UNIVERSITY

Launched November 2025

ESCAPEDE PI: Robert Lillis,
UC Berkeley Space Sciences Laboratory

TECHNOLOGIES TAXONOMY

See full NASA Taxonomy techport.nasa.gov/taxonomy

NASA Taxonomy

Sensors and Instruments (TX08)

Remote Sensing Instruments and Sensors (TX08.1)

Detectors and Focal Planes (TX08.1.1)

MNTA
Magnetic Nano-Transmitter Antenna
20-HTIDS20-0020

TLS
TeraHz Limb Sounder
19-HTIDS19-0027

SIMPoI
Solar Imaging Metasurface Polarimeter
20-HTIDS20-0002

LFDI
Lyot Filter Demonstration Instrument
20-HTIDS20-0004

GMC
Goddard Miniature Coronagraph
22-HTIDS22-0004

SCHI
Scanning Coronal and Heliospheric Imager
23-HTIDS23-0016

MEGA-H
Multi-detector Experiment for next-Gen Applications in Heliophysics
23-HTIDS23-0025

MUVI
Miniaturized UV Imager
18-HTIDS18-0060

EMCCD
Electron Multiplying CCD
20-HTIDS20-0015

CLASS
Compact Lyman-Alpha Spatial heterodyne Spectrometer
20-HTIDS20-0028

WGP
Wire Grid Polarizer
21-HTIDS21-0010

HIRSL
High-Resolution Spectrograph in Lyman-alpha
22-HTIDS22-0007

FTS
Fourier Transform Spectrometer
23-HTIDS23-0022

HSR Soft X-ray CMOS
High Speed Readout Soft X-ray CMOS Detector
19-HTIDS19-0017

HXS SSP
High-Rate X-ray Spectrometer for Solar and Space Physics
24-HTIDS24-0022

CTIS
Computed Tomography Imaging Spectrograph
23-HLCAS23-0011

In Situ Instruments and Sensors (TX08.3)

Field and Particle Sensors (TX08.3.1)

Field Sensors		Particle Sensors		
Magnetic Field	Electric Field	Electrons	Ions/Protons	Neutrals/Neutrons
CHIMERA Hybrid Magnetometer for Smallsats 18-HTIDS18-0010	LIEFSI Laboratory Investigation of Electric Field Sensor Instabilities 20-HTIDS20-0010	MEET Medium Energy Electron Telescope 19-HTIDS19-0001	ACCEPT A Compact Solar Energetic Particle Telescope 19-HTIDS19-0019	IPT Instrumentation for Planetary Thermospheres 21-HTIDS21-0012
HFML High Frequency Magnetic Loop 21-HTIDS21-0004	Grotifer CubeSat for Three-Dimensional Electric Field Measurements 21-HTIDS21-0002	APES-360 Acute Precipitating Electron Spectrometer 360 20-HTIDS20-0021	PRCINI Plasma and Radiation Combined IN-situ Instrument 20-HTIDS20-0009	SONTRAC Solar Neutron TRACKing Instrument 20-HTIDS20-0014 22-HTIDS22-0005 24-HTIDS24-0005
HyMag-ADCS Hybrid Magnetometer-Attitude Determination and Control System 23-HTIDS23-0001	WINS Waves, Instabilities and Noise Spectrometer 22-HTIDS22-0013	HERT High-Energy-Resolution relativistic electron Telescope 20-HTIDS20-0034	MSTR Mass Spectrometry of the Turbopause Region 20-HTIDS20-0027	OCTEA Optics for Compact Two-dimensional Energetic Atom 23-HTIDS23-0004
MOE Mag Magnetometer Based on Magneto-Optical Effects 24-HTIDS24-0036		mDLP miniaturized Double Langmuir Probe 22-HTIDS22-0018	IESADC Ion Electrostatic Analyzer Dynamic Geometric Factor Control 20-HTIDS20-0031	
		MCMS Miniaturized Charging Mitigation Shell 22-HTIDS22-0023	HYPERION High Resolution Plasma Analyzer for Ions 23-HLCAS23-0001	
		SuPREMeS Suprathermal Particle and Relativistic Electron Magnetic Spectrometer 23-HTIDS23-0012	MSWIS Miniature Solar Wind Sensor 23-HTIDS23-0017	Dust/Debris
		MNLP Multi-Needle Langmuir Probe for the Detection of Extremely Small Spatial Structures 23-HTIDS23-0023	SPIDER Shuttered Plasma Instrument for Detecting Environmental Response 24-HTIDS24-0006	LARADO-N Lightsheet Anomaly Resolution and Debris Observation - Neuromorphic 22-HTIDS22-0006
			NTOF Next generation compact time-of-flight plasma instruments for heliophysics 24-HTIDS24-0025	DENTS Debris and meteoroid ENvironment Sensor 22-HTIDS22-0014
			3D-CATS 3D-Cylindrical And Tiny Spectrometer 24-HTIDS24-0039	DDL Debris-Detecting LIDAR Sensor 22-HTIDS22-0020
			HOPE A New HOPE for Ionospheric Outflow and Cold Magnetospheric Plasma Measurements 23-HTIDS23-0024	

HELIOSPHERE

MAGNETOSPHERE

SOLAR SCIENCE

ITM

INTERDISCIPLINARY

Includes select projects from 2018-2024

TECHNOLOGY HIGHLIGHTS

Thermo Sensors: Space Weather Measurements in the Thermosphere

The Thermo series of space weather sensors addresses an increasingly important component of NASA's Heliophysics scientific portfolio. The 2024 Decadal Survey for Solar and Space Physics (Heliophysics) emphasized the importance of space weather from a research perspective, as well as the practicalities of how it affects everyday life on Earth and prioritizes advancement of space weather understanding for NASA Moon to Mars initiatives.

The Thermo series includes Thermo1D (density), Thermo3D (density, 1D winds, temperature), Thermo4D (density, 2D winds, temperature) and Thermo5D (density, 3D winds, temperature). Each sensor is based on economical COTS detectors that sample gas rammed into an accommodation chamber by the relative motion of the host spacecraft. The wind- and temperature-sensitive sensors include a reciprocating baffle that modulates gas flow into the chamber, allowing the analysis needed to derive these quantities. Thermo5D also employs fast shutters adapted from the optical community to modulate the flow.

These sensors provide new capability to explore a key space weather element – Earth's thermosphere. All travel and communication between Earth and space traverse at least part of the thermosphere, and the large number of satellites in low-Earth orbit (LEO) spend their mission lifetime in the thermosphere. Thus, thermospheric weather, which consists of temporal, position-dependent changes in the density, winds, temperature, and composition of the thermospheric gas, has the potential to greatly affect space operations. The operational space fleet is most sensitive to density changes, which can be large and cause appreciable change to objects in LEO. The Thermo sensors can measure these space weather constituents directly from low-resource space platforms.

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TRL 4 >>> 5 >>> 6

EARLY CAREER 2 POSTDOCTORAL 2 UNDERGRAD 1 GRADUATE

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MEGA-H: Simultaneous High-Resolution & Wide Field Corona Coverage

Coronagraphs observe fine features of the solar corona as they emerge from the Sun and propagate outward. This is required to predict the impact of coronal mass ejections on the Earth and eventually Mars. An ideal coronagraph has high spatial resolution to capture fine details and wide field coverage to enable tracing coronal features as they interact and spread, becoming drivers of solar wind. The pixels needed to provide the desired detail is greater than any single detector can provide. A common solution is using an array of detectors that cover the image plane. This requires close packing, which is costly, and leaves coverage gaps.

Multi-detector Experiment for next-Generation Applications in Heliophysics (MEGA-H) overcomes these limitations using pickoff mirrors to direct image parts to three detectors. Separately the detectors cover the full image plane. The image is then combined electronically into a single, seamless, high-resolution image.

The instrument will demonstrate the multi-detector imager concept with an optical instrument that does not include an occulter to block the Sun's disk, but which is suitable for use as a coronagraph during a solar eclipse. Using commercial image sensors and telescope optics, MEGA-H will generate 300-megapixel images that span an image diagonal of 10°, with a pixel size of 1.34 arcsec. The team will use high-dynamic-range imaging and frame co-adding to detect faint corona features across a range of brightnesses.

MEGA-H is designed for deployment on a high-altitude aircraft or balloon and will be used to observe the 2027 solar eclipse from the ground.

SwRI **BAE SYSTEMS**

TRL 3 >>> 3 >>> 4

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AGILE: First In-space Use of Pulse Shape Discrimination

Advanced enerGetic Ion eLEctron tElescope (AGILE) is a novel particle telescope that utilizes – for the first time in space – full pulse shape discrimination (PSD) to identify energetic ions, including solar energetic particles (SEP) and anomalous cosmic rays (ACR), and characterize their spectra for various ion species. AGILE is a compact, low mass, low-power particle telescope suitable for cubesat platforms – an enabler for low-cost, multi-point *in situ* measurements in geospace and interplanetary space. AGILE employs novel algorithms, high heritage solid state detectors, and PSEC4, a state-of-the-art high-speed sampling Application Specific Integrated Circuit (ASIC). This custom ASIC has a high time resolution of ~10 picoseconds. AGILE measures two key characteristics of the amplified pulse of a stopping particle: 'Rise Time' and 'Maximum Amplitude.' Various ions form separated tracks in the rise time-amplitude space, enabling their identification.

AGILE was fully calibrated at NASA's facility at Brookhaven National Laboratory and is set to fly on the GenSat-1 cubesat mission. Built by Genesis Engineering, GenSat-1 is manifested to launch Fall 2026 from NASA's Kennedy Space Center into a high inclination, low earth orbit. On GenSat-1, AGILE will primarily focus on measuring SEPs and trapped ACR ions to advance our understanding of charged particle energization, loss, and transport throughout the heliosphere.

AGILE's compact, low power nature makes it suitable for constellation and formation flying smallsat missions, which could support NASA's Moon to Mars goals.

TRL 3 >>> 6 >>> 8

EARLY CAREER 2 POSTDOCTORAL 2 UNDERGRAD 2 GRADUATE

KU THE UNIVERSITY OF KANSAS

GenSat-1 cubesat showing AGILE's circular aperture on the front face.

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NASA
Goddard
Space Flight Center

Probing the Microphysics of Magnetospheric Dynamics at Ultra-fast Timescales

Recent multi-point observations, particularly from NASA's Magnetospheric Multiscale mission, have revealed that the fundamental processes of reconnection, turbulence, and shock dynamics in space plasmas are more deeply connected than previously thought through microphysics occurring at extremely small time and spatial scales. These studies demonstrate the critical need for all-sky measurements at extremely high cadence (<10 ms) to understand these physical processes.

Currently under development at SwRI, the 3D Cylindrical And Tiny Spectrometer (3D-CATS) is a low resource, wide field-of-view (FOV), nested cylindrical geometry electrostatic analyzer that will provide "fast" electron or ion velocity distribution functions. The 3D-CATS prototype design consists of a sensor head that provides measurements of particles over an energy per charge range of 5 eV/q to >46 keV/q with simultaneous measurement of eight energies and an instantaneous angular FOV of 90°x90°. Three such sensors would take up a 3U cubesat form and would provide a 2π FOV. Two such sensor suite-equipped cubesats, oriented orthogonally to one another, would achieve all-sky coverage. The estimated Size, Weight, and Power (SWaP) for this two cubesat configuration is 6U, ~5 kg, and 5 W.

Beyond the capability to make fast temporal resolution measurements, a low SWaP sensor like 3D-CATS is very compatible with future geophysics mission concepts, including smallsats and multi-satellite platforms. Multiple white papers submitted to the Heliophysics Decadal Survey requested low SWaP instruments for constellation missions. Such instruments are also attractive for understanding space weather, delivering enhanced measurements while providing considerable scope for redundancy.

TRL 4 >>> 5 >>> 6

EARLY CAREER 4 POSTDOCTORAL 2 UNDERGRAD 4 GRADUATE 1

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3D-CATS electrodes. Each channel in an azimuthal "8-channel arm" transmits a different energy.

TECHNOLOGY HIGHLIGHTS

Making Invisible Plasma Instabilities Measurable with Seeded Alfvén Waves

Alfvén waves—oscillations of magnetized plasmas—play a central role in space, from heating the solar corona to shaping solar wind turbulence. Direct measurement of parametric decay instability (PDI), a process in which a large-amplitude Alfvén wave transfers energy to a backward-propagating Alfvén wave and an ion acoustic wave has been a challenge, as wave damping makes it difficult to observe in the lab.

This project developed and validated a new approach using a seeded instability scheme: a small, counter-propagating Alfvén wave is deliberately launched to act as the PDI daughter wave. When encountering a high-power pump Alfvén wave, energy transfer from the pump reduces spatial damping of the seed wave. Comparing seed-wave amplitude with the pump on vs pump off reveals PDI growth rate directly—without requiring instability to overcome the damping threshold.

Using the UCLA Large Plasma Device (LAPD), the team demonstrated clear amplification of the seed wave consistent with theoretical predictions. Notably, this experiment produced the first direct laboratory measurement of the Alfvén wave PDI growth rate, validating theoretical and numerical studies.

These results provide a new experimental capability for studies of nonlinear wave-wave interactions in plasmas. It is broadly applicable to Heliophysics and astrophysics, enabling improved interpretation of spacecraft observations of the solar wind and near-Sun environment and supports NASA's Moon to Mars initiative by advancing the science needed to understand and predict the space environments encountered by explorers.

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22-HTIDS22-0019

GMC: Enabling the Future of Deep Space Solar Coronal Imaging

The Goddard Miniature Coronagraph (GMC) team is designing, fabricating, and testing a small coronagraph component key to enabling the future of coronal imaging capability.

Minimizing coronagraph size and mass while maintaining instrument performance requires a boom to extend the occulter disk system into position. Although other instruments (e.g., magnetometers) have implemented small deployable booms, coronagraph occulters have not used booms due to their strict pointing requirements. The team will advance the pointing accuracy, precision, and stability of a small deployable occulter and test the system's pointing and stray light performance in a unique vacuum tunnel facility designed specifically for coronagraphs.

Understanding - and ultimately forecasting - CME impacts on the geospace environment and throughout the heliosphere is a primary NASA Moon to Mars goal. A small low-weight and -power coronagraph would enable multi-point observations of coronal mass ejections (CMEs) and heliospheric structures, as it could be more easily accommodated on missions leaving the Earth-Sun line, such as missions to L4, L5, or on a solar polar mission. With GMC, such a mission could provide first ever coronagraph images of CME morphologies projected onto the ecliptic plane. This would offer a unique view of the front and interior structure (e.g., flux rope) of Earth-directed CMEs, along with the projected width of the CME in the ecliptic plane. Such data would enable resolving CME width, velocity, morphology, and trajectory in the ecliptic from multi-line-of-sight observations. As CMEs can impact Earth, Moon, or Mars, GMC enables new, significant CME forecasting information toward protecting human assets.

Completed GMC extendable boom and baffle assembly. Alignment plate on front aperture in place of external occulter.

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22-HTIDS22-0004

The Agile, Flexible SPIDER – Doing Critical Science with Less

The Shuttered Plasma Instrument for Detecting Environmental Response (SPIDER) is a novel instrument that applies fundamental low-energy particle measurement principles, optimized to achieve high-impact science goals with fewer resources (size, weight, and power (SWaP), cost, materials, schedule). The design emphasizes ingenuity, modularity, rapid development cycles, and ease of manufacturing without sacrificing key measurement capability. While SPIDER's baseline science objectives are driven by understanding how ionospheric plasma escapes into the magnetosphere—and characterizing the composition of ionospheric outflows—its performance requirements include measuring ions up to 5 keV and achieving a mass resolution of $M/\Delta M = 7$, which are also useful for characterizing solar wind on the lunar surface. Scientists and engineers at APL have designed and built multiple prototype SPIDER sensor heads capable of energy selection and time-of-flight measurements using three key components: 1) an electrostatic shutter enabled by ultrafast switching GaN/SiC high-voltage Field-Effect Transistors, 2) a cylindrical electrostatic analyzer, and 3) an integrated COTS channel electron multiplier capable of operating in 10-5 torr environment. Optional modules—including a front-end ionizer or a rear Einzel-lens focuser/flux reducer—can be incorporated into this highly-configurable platform. To complement the sensor heads, an integrated low-SWaP and cost electronics module has been developed using an agile design approach. In 2026, SPIDER is targeting a suborbital flight technology demonstration featuring a fully-integrated instrument with multiple look directions and expanding its architecture to support extensible measurement capabilities.

SPIDER instrument stack-up.

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MSWIS: Enabling Low-cost, Constellation, and Deep-space Space Weather Missions

Solar wind parameters are critical to understanding the physical processes of space weather and their impacts on Earth, Moon, and Mars. Cubesats are capable, flexible platforms that can be configured for a wide range of science/commercial mission profiles, either as a standalone platform, as a daughter spacecraft, or in swarms and constellations. Miniature Solar Wind Sensor (MSWIS) is a compact, low-power, high-performance (1U, 1.5 kg, 4.7 W) solar wind analyzer for measuring ion velocity distribution functions (VDFs) and determining bulk solar wind moments with accuracies comparable to state-of-the-art sensors. MSWIS's novel design gives an energy per charge (E/q) range of 100 eV/q to >10 keV/q with 7% resolution. The sensor total FOV covers 44°x44° with 132 4°x4° Electrostatic Analyzer (ESA) segments. Each ESA segment points to different arrival directions, so MSWIS can instantaneously image 2D angle (elevation x azimuth) distributions of incoming solar wind protons and particles with identical E/q. Sweeping a single internal electrode alters the E/q step and completes the particle 3D VDFs and solar wind moments (velocity, density, perpendicular and parallel temperatures) can be accurately calculated for protons and particles.

The team has completed the MSWIS initial proof-of-concept study and sensor designing/packaging efforts. It successfully achieved the 1U size goal, including electronics needed to operate, control, and communicate with spacecraft. A compact, versatile solar wind sensor like MSWIS will be attractive to future Heliophysics and planetary missions. It will also be of interest to space weather researchers for predicting and modeling space environment variability across the solar system.

MSWIS mechanical package (10x10x9.6 cm) with communication and power connectors at the bottom.

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23-HTIDS23-0017

TECHNOLOGY HIGHLIGHTS

SuPREMeS: A Compact Monitor for Hazardous Radiation in Space

The Suprathermal Particle and Relativistic Electron Magnetic Spectrometer (SuPREMeS) is a novel and innovative instrument design that promises to deliver a next-generation, high-performance, and low-resource option for measurements of energetic particles in space. The goal of this Instrument Technology Development effort is to advance the instrument design from Technology Readiness Level 3 to TRL 6 by the end of the effort, providing a new instrument that will address science related to solar energetic particles, cosmic rays, and Earth's and other planetary bodies' radiation belts.

The SuPREMeS design uses an array of ultra-strong, rare-earth element magnets to deflect, then precisely and accurately measure, relativistic electrons in the space environment. SuPREMeS' strong magnets and compact design offers multiple advantages, including an extended energy range, background characterization and removal, and low stray magnetic fields. The full instrument is approximately the size of a large coffee can, yet it boasts an extraordinary and unprecedented dynamic range and level of performance.

SuPREMeS will measure energetic particles that result in hazardous radiation exposure to satellites and astronauts in space. As a radiation belt monitor, SuPREMeS will be effective at characterizing the high levels of trapped radiation in Earth's geomagnetic field that disrupt satellite systems or can even result in a total system failure. As a monitor for solar energetic particles, SuPREMeS offers a compact, low-resource, and high-performance option for characterizing the environment and safeguarding astronauts in operations extending from the Moon to Mars.

An array of ultra-strong, rare-earth bar magnets bend relativistic electrons to different detection locations based on their electron energy.

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SCHI: Tracking Solar Eruptions with Novel Metasurface Technology

A team at APL is seeking to develop a visible-light telescope to capture high-resolution, wide field-of-view (FOV) images of the solar corona, while simultaneously reducing instrument size and complexity. Visible-light observations of the corona allow tracking of large-scale transients, including coronal mass ejections (CMEs), which are key drivers of space weather. Tracking CMEs with higher spatial resolution and signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) improves forecasting of hazardous conditions at Earth, in cislunar space, and along the route to Mars and on its surface, assisting in NASA's Moon to Mars initiative.

Scanning Coronal and Heliospheric Imager (SCHI) is a novel visible-light telescope that leverages cutting-edge hybrid metasurface Risley prisms (MRPs) to produce high-resolution, wide-FOV maps of the solar corona in a compact 6U+ cubesat-compatible form factor and without the need for complex scanning mechanisms. Using hybrid MRPs, the telescope can "point" to any location simply by adjusting the relative rotation of the MRPs. This enables rapid mapping of a large field of regard with a small instantaneous FOV, providing improved spatial resolution and SNR. Metasurfaces, composed of sub-wavelength posts tailored to direct and filter an incoming beam, offer greater design flexibility than refractive optics alone, reducing distortion and enabling a smaller form factor. The versatile MRPs could also include polarimetric information for estimating 3D morphologies or extend into the near-infrared to search for near-Earth objects.

The team is currently demonstrating design and construction of these high-efficiency hybrid MRPs and assessing performance of the full optical system. Future work will advance the miniaturized optical system's space-readiness and demonstrate SCHI in space.

Test setup of a sample metasurface array with a magnified image of sub-wavelength metasurface posts.

Juliana Vievering

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23-HTIDS23-0016

EARLY CAREER PI SPOTLIGHT

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Dr. Mojtaba Akhavan-Tafti is an Associate Research Scientist at the University of Michigan. His research interests include studying plasma instabilities in the heliosphere using observations, simulations, and laboratory experiments. He is a team member of NASA's flagship Parker Solar Probe (PSP) mission. He is the Principal Investigator of the Space Weather Investigation Frontier (SWIFT) mission concept. Using flight-ready solar sail technology, SWIFT aims to unravel the 3D structure and temporal evolution of mesoscale solar wind structures that drive terrestrial space weather from inside Sun-Earth Lagrange Point 1. He also teaches multidisciplinary courses on space systems and instrumentation design and management.

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23-HTIDS23-0008

Dr. Amy Gall is an Assistant Professor at Auburn University and a Research Associate at the Smithsonian Astrophysical Observatory (SAO). She works with the SAO Electron Beam Ion Trap facility to create and confine highly charged ions for high-precision spectroscopic studies. Her research investigates atomic processes in collisionally ionized plasmas and provides benchmark measurements that improve the atomic databases used to interpret solar and astrophysical observations. She is currently conducting high-resolution X-ray and extreme-ultraviolet measurements in support of Heliophysics missions such as Solar-C, MUSE, ECCCO, and EUNIS, as well as astrophysics missions, including XRISM and Athena.

Ed Thiemann

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23-HTIDS23-0022

Dr. Ed Thiemann develops new instruments for space-based ultraviolet astronomy. He seeks to understand variations in the upper atmospheres of Earth and other planets. This fascinating region is sensitive to changes on the Sun, which can produce solar storms, and changes in the lower atmosphere, which produces a continuous flow of atmospheric waves. These processes leave signatures in faint ultraviolet emissions only visible using specialized space-based instruments.

He is actively involved in multiple NASA missions, including as the lead of the Occultation Wave Limb Sounder (OWLS) mission, EUV Monitor onboard the Mars MAVEN orbiter, and Total Irradiance Monitor (TIM) on the upcoming TSIS-2 mission.

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23-HTIDS23-0016

Dr. Juliana Vievering is a solar physicist at the Johns Hopkins Applied Physics Laboratory. She received her PhD in 2019 from the University of Minnesota, working with Dr. Lindsay Glesener on the Focusing Optics X-ray Solar Imager (FOXSI-3) sounding rocket experiment and analysis of X-ray emission from solar and stellar flares. Her research interests include the nature of energy release during solar eruptive events, flare prediction for coordinated observations and space weather applications, and novel solar instrumentation development. She is excited to be working with a team of APL solar physicists, metasurface engineers, and optical engineers on a NASA grant to develop novel metasurface technology for a scanning coronal and heliospheric imager.

INTERDISCIPLINARY COLLABORATIONS

The rapid evolution of space exploration demands a departure from traditional siloed research and technology development, favoring instead a collaborative model where diverse scientific disciplines converge. Our goal is to expand our horizons through interdisciplinary synergy.

This year's portfolio highlights the power of interdisciplinary partnerships. From the **Microwave Electrojet Magnetogram (MEM)** instrument, a collaboration between Heliophysics and Earth Sciences currently flying on the Electrojet Zeeman Imaging Explorer (EZIE) mission, to the **High Resolution Spectrograph in Lyman- α (HIRSL)** instrument, which leverages Planetary Science Expertise, and the **Helium, Oxygen, Proton, and Electron (HOPE)** instrument, which has future Planetary Science applications. By integrating disparate expertise, we are not only optimizing resource allocation but also accelerating the development of versatile technologies that serve the broader scientific community.

Blue Canyon Technologies technicians Davy Hong and Dave Biancalana attach a solar array to the bus of the EZIE cubesat.

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MEM: Remotely Sensing Ionospheric Electrojets from a Smallsat Constellation

The NASA Heliophysics Division's cost-effective Electrojet Zeeman Imaging Explorer (EZIE) mission of opportunity focuses on a science problem ideally suited to today's smallsat technologies by combining novel miniature instrument technology, state-of-art commercial cubesats, propulsion-less constellation management, and a new remote sensing technique.

At the heart of the mission are three Microwave Electrojet Magnetogram (MEM) instruments developed leveraging HESTO and Earth Science Technology Office (ESTO) investments.

Short-lived geomagnetic substorms release energy into Earth's ionosphere, causing the aurora (northern/southern lights) and disrupting radio communications, GPS accuracy, and satellite tracking/operations. The spatiotemporal structure of the ionospheric electrojets, which couple Earth and space and flow at the edge of space, are NASA science and space weather research priorities. Electrojet currents cause small perturbations to Earth's magnetic field, but *in situ* measurement of the geomagnetic field at very low Earth orbit (VLEO) altitudes (below ~350 km) is challenging, as it is too high for sustained suborbital observations (e.g., balloons, rockets) and too low for orbiting satellites because of atmospheric drag. Thus, flying a fleet of *in situ* magnetometers on spacecraft in VLEO is not technically feasible.

EZIE remotely senses the fingerprint of electrojet current-induced magnetic field perturbations through Zeeman splitting of the 118-GHz oxygen thermal emission near the electrojets (~105 km altitude). Four compact spectropolarimeters in each of the three MEM instruments (12 total radiometers) onboard three 6U cubesats fly in an in-line, string-of-pearls orbit configuration to measure the geomagnetic field and map the 2D electrojet structure. Each MEM payload, built by JPL, has four polarimetric receivers that feed a digital backend where all Stokes polarization parameters are calculated. The MEM receivers have heritage from NASA ground-based, airborne, and space-borne radiometers, including TEMPEST-D, GeoSTAR, HAMMR, and YTHP. The digital backend field programmable gate array-based design also leverages NASA missions (e.g., CubeRRR, PALS). However, the MEM design has unique aspects, including that it does not use a diode-detector and instead digitizes a down-converted radio frequency (RF) signal for radiance calculation and that it is one of the first digital spectrometers integrated with a mm-wave radiometer. The MEM RF design measures both V and H polarizations, and the digital backend allows third and

Artist's illustration of the three EZIE 6U CubeSat flying in a pearl-on-a-string configuration.

fourth Stokes parameters to be digitally calculated over the spectra. Variable temporal sampling of Earth's high-latitude auroral region is accomplished solely by using differential drag maneuvers to control the inter-satellite spacing. By combining maps from the three spacecraft, the structure and temporal evolutions of the electrojet are determined over a period of several minutes.

The EZIE constellation launched March 15, 2025, on a SpaceX Transporter-13 rideshare and was deployed into low Earth orbit (590 km). The EZIE cubesats were developed commercially by Blue Canyon Technologies, which has enabled many NASA smallsat missions. As of spring 2026, EZIE has successfully completed its first northern and southern auroral electrojet seasons, observing numerous geomagnetic storms and substorms and capturing the spatial and temporal variability of electrojets.

EZIE/MEM instrument.

The HIRSL team using a red laser to align the Echelle diffraction grating with the micro-channel plate detector.

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HIRSL: Characterizing the Hydrogen Wall and Planetary Water in the Solar System

A Boston University team has redesigned a high-heritage system originally developed for observations of Venus and Mars to achieve novel measurement capabilities by extending the optical path and folding it into a space-deployable configuration. The resulting instrument concept, the High Resolution Spectrograph in Lyman- α (HIRSL), achieves higher spectral resolution and efficiency while maintaining compact size, low power usage, and low mass.

HIRSL's demonstrated spectral resolution surpasses state-of-the-art systems, enabling unprecedented discernment between different populations of atoms critical to understanding far ultraviolet (FUV) emissions—including hydrogen (H) Lyman- α , deuterium (D) Lyman- α , and oxygen (O) triplet emissions—with ~5 km/s resolution. The team is using these observations to measure distinct kinetic properties (velocities, number densities, temperatures) of the FUV-emitting atoms. A key HIRSL capability is distinguishing the different populations of H atoms that make up the Interplanetary Medium, separating the signatures of unperturbed Interstellar Medium H atoms from Hydrogen Wall H atoms to understand the dynamics at the far edge of our Solar System—a critical objective for NASA's planned Interstellar Probe (ISP) mission. Another HIRSL capability is to characterize the abundance of water-originating atoms in planetary atmospheres and cometary exospheres to quantify present-day water content and loss from a planetary body. In addition to hardware, the HIRSL team is developing software to optimize the data-reduction and analysis pipeline for detecting faint and strong emissions, as well as to accommodate the dynamic background signal produced in the measured spectra due to potential proximity to a radioisotope thermoelectric generator that may be used on ISP. These combined efforts culminate in a novel and adaptable FUV system that can be applied to a range of Solar System targets, accommodate placement on spacecraft or the lunar surface to support America's return to the Moon, and can help better understand the Martian atmosphere to support future Mars exploration.

Ionospheric outflow schematic.

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A New HOPE for Ionospheric Outflow and Cold Magnetospheric Plasma Measurements

The space physics team at Los Alamos National Laboratory (LANL), is designing, fabricating, and testing a new Helium, Oxygen, Proton, and Electron (HOPE) ion mass spectrometer to provide exquisite energy resolution of low energy, "cold" ions and electrons, otherwise known as space plasma. These cold plasma populations

originate as ionospheric outflow from Earth's polar regions and travel throughout the magnetosphere, driving critical processes that determine magnetosphere structure and dynamics. These cold plasma populations have never been adequately measured due to difficulties associated with instrument energy resolution and effects of the host satellite interacting with the space environment. The lack of accurate measurements makes answering some of today's most significant science questions extremely difficult, if not impossible. Answering these questions requires innovations in sensor design and associated techniques to obtain high-fidelity measurements of the cold ion and electron populations in the magnetosphere.

The HOPE instrument is the only ion mass spectrometer to have successfully made observations through the heart of the radiation belts, thus making the New HOPE instrument an ideal candidate for future cold plasma missions. By leveraging HOPE electronics heritage, the LANL team will provide an instrument capable of making ion composition measurements with exquisite energy resolution while being subjected to the brutal environment within the radiation belts.

The team will achieve the New HOPE by adding a retarding potential analyzer (RPA) to the sensor. This upgraded HOPE instrument will be ideal for obtaining high energy resolution observations of low-energy (0.5 to 100 eV) ion populations of ionospheric outflow and cold magnetospheric space plasma. By refurbishing and upgrading a HOPE Engineering Model to include the RPA front-end, the team will demonstrate the ability to make high energy resolution measurements of cold ion and cold electrons. New HOPE will be tested and characterized against photoelectrons and a low energy plasma source as a function of simulated spacecraft potential at LANL's test facilities.

HELIOTECH: Heliophysics Technology Symposium

HELIOTECH2025 attendees at APL in Laurel, MD. Image Credit: APL

HELIOTECH2025 was our first joint symposium. This year we partnered with NASA's Suborbital program to foster collaboration between technologists and flight Principal Investigators. Held September 8–12 at the Johns Hopkins Applied Physics Laboratory (APL), in Laurel MD, HELIOTECH2025 was a tremendous success, attended by over 170 individuals in person and over 200 virtually. It offered a venue for innovation, learning, and strengthening valuable collaborations between the technologists and the Suborbital community.

The symposium catalyzed partnership opportunities to infuse technologies into flight proposals to advance science. It featured a panel of commercial rideshare companies to showcase flight opportunities to the community, enabling maturation of technologies, and low-cost science returns. We're looking forward to seeing you at HELIOTECH2026.

HELIOTECH2025 attendees at APL in Laurel, MD. Image Credit: APL

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SUBORBITAL PROGRAM

The suborbital program provides a path for advancing the technology readiness levels of future space flight technologies.

Turbulent Oxygen Mixing EXperiment Plus (TOMEX+)

Jim Clemmons

University of New Hampshire
16-HTIDS16_2-0073

In August 2025, the three-rocket TOMEX+ mission dodged weather generated by hurricane Erin to launch from NASA's Wallops Flight Facility into an event at the Earth's turbopause (~90 km altitude). This investigation was conceived to improve our understanding of how turbulence and the mixing of atomic oxygen are related to each other and to underlying atmospheric instabilities. It focused on three objectives: determining how the vertical profile of the atomic oxygen mixing ratio varies near the turbopause, resolving horizontal variations in the atomic oxygen density related to variations in turbulent fluctuations, and characterizing the three-dimensional turbulence spectrum and its spatial variability.

First Atmospheric Lidar in Space

The main TOMEX+ instrument was used to measure the sodium layer—a permanent feature of the mesopause/turbopause region—and its density variations, which reflect its turbulent state. This was accomplished using light detection and ranging (lidar) laser to excite sodium atoms and measure the light they emit. TOMEX+ also required sounding rocket vehicle innovations, including a controlled flat spin for the main science payload (sounding rockets are typically spun up during launch for stability), procedures for testing a payload spinning about a transverse axis, producing a slowly rotating spin for the sub-payload to align closely to the rocket velocity direction, and placing the recovery system in the middle of the built-up payload (it is usually in the nose cone). All instruments recorded excellent data, in space and on the ground. The data will allow the team to assess the degree of turbulence and its extent, the thermospheric winds, which instabilities were active, and how atomic oxygen is mixed by these phenomena. The data are currently under analysis, with preliminary results showing TOMEX+ captured the turbulence, instabilities, and gravity waves that were its intended target.

TOMEX+ spaceborne lidar.

The Low-Cost Access to Space (LCAS) program seeks to advance science, as well as advance the development and demonstration of technologies to enable future investigations. Highlighted are some technologies developed, infused, and demonstrated through LCAS.

Full-disk Ultraviolet Rocket Spectrometer (FURST)

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24-LCAS24-0017

The FURST instrument observes the far ultraviolet (FUV) spectrum of the Sun as a star, putting the Sun into context with other stars observed in the FUV by the Hubble Space Telescope. FURST will aid in understanding the heating of the Sun's lower solar atmosphere and with making detailed comparisons to other Sun-like stars. FURST was launched from White Sands Missile Range on September 3, 2024. The vehicle and instrument functioned as expected, but a stray light leak in the instrument saturated the detector. Based on extensive testing, the team has modified the instrument to improve stray light suppression by more than a factor of 100. After completing radiometric calibration, FURST will re-fly to complete its observations.

Novel Spectrometer Design

The principal challenge of the FURST mission is obtaining an unbiased sample of the full Sun, observed as if it were a distant star. This is accomplished using a convex, reflective cylindrical feed optic that forms a virtual image of the Sun only 15 microns wide, presenting the full Sun as a golden thread of light that illuminates the spectrometer optics. The second challenge is sampling a wide swath of wavelengths (120-180 nm) at very high spectral resolution. To accomplish this, FURST cycles through an array of seven feed optics, each positioned to capture a different segment of the solar spectrum. Combining the data obtained by the seven feed optics results in a precisely calibrated spectrum more than 25,000 pixels wide.

The FURST instrument during assembly.

Ion-Neutral Coupling during Active Aurora 2 (INCAA-2)

Stephen Kaeppler

Clemson University
24-LCAS24-0008

The INCAA-2 sounding rocket mission, a follow-on to the successful INCAA launch in April 2022, addresses the important question of how energy is transferred from the magnetosphere into the ionosphere-thermosphere system. This energy deposition can have significant impacts on space weather, such as generating traveling ionospheric disturbances that affect high-frequency radio wave propagation. This mission focuses specifically on the pre-midnight magnetic local time sector, where the largest heating rates have been observed. The goal is to measure the altitude-resolved electric fields, conductivities, currents, and neutral winds from two sounding rocket salvos. Each will have a chemical tracer payload and an instrumented payload. Launch will take place no earlier than 2028 from the Poker Flat Research Range in Alaska.

Residual Gas Analyzer Neutral Mass Spectrometer

Clemson University (CU) has been developing a neutral mass spectrometer based on a commercially available residual gas analyzer. One of the consequences of significant Joule heating can be changes in composition, which have been scantily measured in the 90-150 km altitude of Earth's atmosphere—the altitudes used by very low Earth orbiters (VLEO). The most recent previous neutral mass spectrometer was flown on a sounding rocket in the 1990s. This technology development leverages existing CU laboratory capabilities and expertise to ruggedize, calibrate, and test a residual gas analyzer for use at these altitudes. The NASA South Carolina Space Grant Consortium provided initial seed funding to purchase an MKS High Pressure Quadrupole (HPQ3) residual gas analyzer, which is currently being used as a testbed for this technology development.

First INCAA launch, April 2022.

Ground Imaging to Rocket investigations of Auroral Fast Features (GIRAFF)

Robert Michell

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19-HFORT19-0029

The GIRAFF mission targeted the fastest optical variations observed within the aurora. These are the flickering aurora and fast pulsating aurora, which can contain temporal modulations of up to 30 times/second and 10 times/second, respectively. GIRAFF flew two identical payloads, one targeting each of these aurora types, with the science goal of figuring out where in space these auroral modulations are happening.

In 2025, the first rocket launched February 2 into a pulsating auroral event. The second launched February 9 into a series of small-scale active auroral arcs in search of flickering aurora. A primary GIRAFF mission goal was to combine the *in situ* measurements with high-resolution ground-based auroral imaging from a downrange site in Venetie, AK, situated under the highest point of the rocket's trajectory. This enabled simultaneous one-to-one comparison between the rocket measurements and the aurora.

Emma Mirizio and Danjing Chen completing final assembly on a GIRAFF payload.

APES, CHIMPS, and APES-360: High Resolution Electron Measurements

A critical aspect of GIRAFF was measuring precipitating electrons with high time-resolution (1 millisecond per energy spectrum) in one look-direction. This was accomplished using the Acute Precipitating Electron Spectrometer (APES). Two technology demonstration instruments provided additional electron measurements: Capped-Hemispherical Instrument for Measuring Pitch-angle Spectra (CHIMPS), supplying a high angular resolution of 3 degrees and a standard 10 Hz sample rate, and APES-360, developed under HTiDeS, which combines aspects of APES with multiple look directions. A third tech instrument, the Ion Velocity Mass Spectrometer (IVMS), developed under NASA's GSFC's Internal Research and Development (IRAD) program, also flew on GIRAFF.

STUDENT TECHNOLOGISTS

HESTO is tasked with supporting the maturation of Heliophysics Technology investments and facilitating their infusion into future spaceflight missions. To further this goal, HESTO is working to create a dynamic, interactive science and technology community of current and future thinkers striving to develop tomorrow's solutions to our biggest Heliophysics questions. HESTO actively engages and encourages student technologists toward career paths that develop our future research, technology, and mission principal investigators. HESTO supports:

Discovery through transformative technological advancements fueled by a community that includes current experts along with those who will be the future drivers of technology and science discovery.

Opportunity for students at all education levels – high school, undergraduate, graduate, and post-doctoral – as well as for cross-cutting technology teams to participate in events that bring together current principal investigators with future scientists and technologists, as well as multidisciplinary viewpoints from outside the established Heliophysics community.

Collaboration to foster cooperation and information sharing, catalyzing collaborative technological advancement between scientific disciplines, technology development pathways, and current and future scientists and technologists.

AUBURN UNIVERSITY

- * Rahul Banka ASTROPHYSICAL SCIENCES
- ❖ Alistair Fernandes PHYSICS
- ◆ Saylor Jordan AEROSPACE
- ❖ Tithi Patel AEROSPACE
- ❖ Will Teague PHYSICS

BOSTON UNIVERSITY

- ❖ Ashley Gomez ELECTRICAL & COMPUTER ENGINEERING
- * Patrick Lierle ASTRONOMY

CATHOLIC UNIVERSITY OF AMERICA

- * Mariana Jeunon Barros Ferreira PHYSICS

CLEMSON UNIVERSITY

- * Abrar Chowdhury PHYSICS
- * Hunter Staiger PHYSICS

EMBRY-RIDDLE AERONAUTICAL UNIVERSITY

- ❖ Nathan Graves ENGINEERING PHYSICS
- ◆ Ian Holland ENGINEERING PHYSICS

LULEÅ UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY, SWEDEN

- * Shreni N. Sonanikar SPACE TECHNOLOGY & INSTRUMENTATION

NORTHERN BURLINGTON COUNTY REGIONAL HIGH SCHOOL

- Alma Alex N/A

PRINCETON UNIVERSITY

- * Kendra Bergstedt ASTROPHYSICAL SCIENCES
- * Steve Majeski ASTROPHYSICAL SCIENCES
- * Josh Pawlak ASTROPHYSICAL SCIENCES
- * Adam Robbins ASTROPHYSICAL SCIENCES
- * Rachel Wang ASTROPHYSICAL SCIENCES

SOUTHWEST RESEARCH INSTITUTE (SWRI)

- ❖ Jonathan Gasser PHYSICS
- ❖ Jared Schroeder PHYSICS

STANFORD UNIVERSITY

- * Spencer Bell MECHANICAL ENGINEERING

TUFTS UNIVERSITY

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**Does not include all student participants from 2025*

BOLD VISIONS FOR HELIOPHYSICS

A Decade of Innovation and Discovery – Building the Foundation of a Great Future

As we enter 2026, the NASA Heliophysics Technology Program’s (HTP) forward-looking posture is ready to meet the challenges of a rapidly-evolving space-based landscape. Our purpose is clear: develop the transformative technologies required to achieve the ambitious vision set forth in the 2024 Decadal Survey for Solar and Space Physics and advance NASA’s Moon to Mars initiative. This aligns with the survey’s bold vision “to discover the secrets of the local cosmos and to expand and safeguard humanity’s home in space” and its sustaining mission “to explore our habitable cosmos in the service of humanity.”

To turn vision into reality, HTP serves as an engine of innovation, lowering the barriers to entry for high-impact science and new instrumentation. We are committed to developing the next generation of technologies that will safeguard our planet Earth and enable a deeper understanding of the Sun-Earth connection to protect space-based assets while supporting the expansion of humanity’s presence in the solar system.

HTP’s strategy is intrinsically linked to NASA’s broader exploration goals. As the United States returns to the Moon and prepares for human missions to Mars, HTP is prioritizing development of resilient and miniaturized technologies to support these objectives. Innovations funded through HTP will enable our country to leverage Gateway, future lunar platforms, and deep-space trajectories to conduct critical science that serves to protect our astronauts and spacecraft from the volatile nature of space weather.

The NASA Heliophysics Division goal to “launch more science to space faster” will unlock a broader space economy and act as a force multiplier for NASA science and technology investments. To accomplish this, the Division has a four-pillared strategy, guiding HTP:

Leaner, Faster, More Efficient: Streamline technology maturation pipelines and leverage commercial partnerships to reduce the time from idea to laboratory concept to orbital deployment.

Prioritize Societal Benefit and Immediacy: Focus on “science in action” – technologies that provide near-real-time data to protect critical infrastructure on Earth, in orbit, and throughout the solar system.

Results-Driven Science: Invest in technologies that answer the highest-priority science questions of the next decade, ensuring every HTP-funded technology has a clear path to answering fundamental cosmic questions and supporting humanity’s growth to the stars.

Focused Space Weather Science: Champion development of advanced instrumentation specifically designed to improve space weather forecasting accuracy and lead-time.

By pushing the boundaries of science and redefining what is possible, HTP keeps NASA at the forefront of space physics and technology developments, preparing humanity to explore our cosmic neighborhood and safeguard our home planet for generations to come.

“The frontier of our knowledge is moving inevitably outward. It has already embraced the Moon... but the frontier is moving on. There is water, there is carbon dioxide, there is sunlight [the Sun]—these are the prerequisites for life. Whether or not there is life on Mars now, there will be by the end of this century.” – Carl Sagan

“Keep your face always toward the sunshine - and shadows will fall behind you.” – Walt Whitman

“The Moon is the first milestone on the road to the stars.” – Arthur C. Clarke

“Mars is empty now. Five hundred years from now, it’ll be full of people.” – Ray Bradbury

2025

- Q1 2024 Heliophysics Technology Annual Report Released
- Q2 Pathfinder Call for Proposals
- Q3 Pathfinder Selections
HELIOTECH/Suborbital 2025
- Q4 American Geophysical Union (AGU) Fall Meeting

2026

- Q1 ROSES-2025 H-TIDeS Released
2025 Annual Technology Report Released
Pathfinder Call for Proposals
- Q2 ROSES-2025 H-TIDeS Proposals Due
Pathfinder Selections
- Q3 ROSES-2025 H-TIDeS Selections
ROSES-2026 Anticipated Release
HELIOTECH/Orbital Flight 2026
- Q4 American Geophysical Union (AGU) Fall Meeting

2027

- Q1 2026 Annual Technology Report Released

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About the Cover

By powering advancements in technology, scientific observation, and modeling, HESTO serves as a fundamental enabler – strengthening America’s ability to predict space weather, protect astronauts and assets, and drive development of next-generation solutions. These capabilities form the foundation of a new era of human exploration, one that links our understanding of the Sun to missions to the Moon and Mars as we venture deeper into the solar system. The artist’s inspiration reflects this forward momentum. Fueled by the technologies that will carry us beyond Earth, the cover centers the Sun as NASA’s engine of technological innovation and scientific insight. The gears and circuitry symbolize the technologies needed for humanity to extend its foothold farther into the solar system, connecting today’s progress to the nation’s long-term exploration goals. Illustration Credit: NASA/Christa Harmon

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